

Oceans and Coasts

Annual Science Report

2025

Report No. 25

forestry, fisheries
& the environment

Department:
Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

Oceans and Coasts

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2025

Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION

i

MONITORING PROGRAMMES

1. Indicator for coastal eutrophication along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line.....	1
2. Chlorophyll <i>a</i> variability on the west and south coasts	2
3. Surface chlorophyll <i>a</i> concentrations along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line.....	4
4. Microzooplankton abundance in the Southern Benguela.....	6
5. From local shores to global standards: baseline plastics survey at Strandfontein Beach.....	7
6. A standardised approach to monitoring benthic invertebrate communities in MPAs....	8
7. First long-term monitoring observations of the benthic invertebrate community in the Robben Island MPA.....	9
8. The resilience of crowned cormorants amidst general seabird decline.....	10
9. Temporal variability and changes in fin whale song characteristics off the west coast of South Africa.....	11
10. Long-term variability in bottom temperature on the Prince Edward Islands shelf.....	12
11. Long-term observations of currents on the Prince Edward Islands shelf.....	14
12. Warming and weaker currents around the Prince Edward Islands over the past five years.....	16

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

13. Surface nutrient distributions around Gough Island.....	18
14. Vertical distribution of nutrients around Gough Island.....	19
15. Distribution and fluxes of dissolved trace metal iron around Gough Island.....	20
16. The tiny plankton of the South Atlantic Ocean	21
17. Picophytoplankton communities in the southern Benguela during summer and winter	22
18. Surface nutrient ratios along the SAMBA Monitoring Line during early spring 2025..	23
19. The effects of aquaculture effluent on rocky shore organisms in Marshstrand, East London.....	24
20. Effects of experimental manipulations of the density of <i>Cymbula granatina</i> on macro algal cover.....	25
21. Influence of flow variability on benthic macrofaunal communities in fluvially dominated estuaries.....	26
22. The role of river flow in shaping nursery value for larval fishes in a temperate estuary.....	27
23. Investigating the role of diel vertical migration in larval connectivity modelling.....	28
24. Seasonal variations in the Agulhas Current density structure.....	29
25. Drivers of Agulhas Current circulation and variability in a regional ocean model.....	30
26. The Prince Edward Islands as a forerunner in global island ecosystem research.....	31

27. Distributions of carbonate system parameters around the Prince Edward Islands in 2025.....	32
28. Interannual differences in zooplankton community structure at the Prince Edward Islands.....	33
29. Environmental influence on zooplankton community structure at the Prince Edward Islands.....	34
30. The influence of sampling approach on zooplankton monitoring.....	35
31. DNA metabarcoding of marine zooplankton at the Prince Edward Islands (2022–2024).....	36
32. DNA metabarcoding reveals land-ocean interactions at the Prince Edward Islands.....	37
33. Near-surface distributions of picophytoplankton in the Southern Ocean.....	38
34. Distribution of picophytoplankton near Antarctica in January 2025.....	39

SCIENCE TO POLICY

35. International workshop on pelagic ecoregionalisation of the Indian sub-Antarctic high seas.....	40
36. South Africa at the forefront: nuclear science solutions for plastic pollution.....	41

PLATFORMS, TECHNOLOGY & INNOVATION

37. Harmonising United Nations protocols for monitoring plastic pollution.....	42
38. DNA mini-barcode primers improve species detection rates in metabarcoding of marine zooplankton.....	43
39. A crowdsourced gillnet reporting application to support coastal compliance and enforcement.....	44

TRAINING & OUTREACH

40. Building capacity for Continuous Plankton Recorder sample analysis.....	45
41. Strengthening South Africa’s plastics monitoring network: insights from the SAMP Network Workshop 2025.....	46

OUTPUTS FOR 2025

Peer-reviewed publications.....	47
Presentations at symposia, conferences and workshops.....	47
Published datasets.....	51
Published reports.....	58
Theses.....	58

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Most staff members of the Chief Directorate: Oceans & Coastal Research contributed in one way or another to the contents and production of the Oceans and Coasts Annual Science Report, 2025. The Department wishes to express its appreciation to the many other agencies that have contributed to the work presented in this report. The at-sea, ship-based work and many coastal field trips for data collection and community engagements undertaken by the Branch: Oceans and Coasts are facilitated by the Chief Directorate's science managers and made possible by the various units within the Branch's Corporate Management Services and Financial Management Services.

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COVER IMAGE

Aerial view of Koppie Alleen Beach within the De Hoop Marine Protected Area, Western Cape

Credit: Jean Tresfon - Marine Conservation Photographer

RPxx/2026

ISBN:

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.21065301

INTRODUCTION

2025 marked a significant year in ocean governance, with South Africa playing a prominent role as it assumed the G20 presidency for the first time. At the UN Ocean Conference (UNOC3), held in Nice, France (9-13 June 2025), a political declaration titled “Our Ocean, Our Future: United for Urgent Action” was adopted by more than 170 countries. The declaration sought to shift rhetoric on ocean issues towards action by reaffirming countries’ commitments to Sustainable Development Goal 14 (SDG 14), supported by billions of dollars in new pledges for conservation, marine protected areas (MPAs) and blue finance.

Another key outcome of the declaration was the acceleration of the BBNJ (Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction) Treaty. South Africa became a signatory to the Treaty at UNOC3 and, although ratification (which requires parliamentary approval) is still pending, the country has played an important role in shaping its implementation arrangements as one of only three African states serving as bureau members of the BBNJ Preparatory Commission. This highlights South Africa’s growing leadership in multilateral ocean governance, championing African priorities and Global South perspectives while advancing ocean sustainability and high-seas conservation. These efforts align closely with the theme of South Africa’s 2025 G20 presidency: “Solidarity, Equality, Sustainability”.

South Africa’s G20 Presidency included particular focus on sustainable ocean governance through marine spatial planning (MSP), combatting marine pollution, and supporting a just transition to a sustainable blue economy that delivers equitable benefits to coastal communities. Technical papers on MSP and marine litter, commissioned by DFFE to inform discussions within the 2025 G20 Environment and Climate Sustainability Working Group, are available in the publication [ECSWG-G20-Technical-Papers-October-2025-Final.pdf](#)

Several key areas of work led by the DFFE Branch: Oceans and Coasts are directly aligned with the objectives and focus areas of the G20 ocean agenda. These include MSP, which is currently being developed to zone ocean space for sustainable use and conservation; MPA management and expansion to conserve biodiversity and critical habitats while supporting sustainable fisheries; the Ocean Economy Master Plan, which aims to unlock, stabilise, revive, and grow key sub-sectors of South Africa’s ocean economy; and the National Coastal Management Programme, which includes climate adaptation and the management of pollution among its priorities.

Science-based guidance and recommendations are essential for advancing progress and informing policy and decision-making priorities such as those highlighted above, and the activities conducted by Oceans and Coastal Research (OC Research) are integral to this. Considerable resources and effort are

devoted to developing and maintaining long-term monitoring programmes that provide sustained observations of key aspects of the marine environment. These include ocean temperature, chlorophyll concentration, species trends over time, and many other physical, chemical and biological parameters. Regularly updated long-term datasets enable the assessment of environmental variability and change, biodiversity responses to changing environmental conditions, and the impacts of human activities on marine ecosystems.

OC Research also conducts foundational research in oceanography and marine biodiversity to improve and expand our understanding of marine systems. This includes, for example, documenting physical and chemical processes such as ocean current dynamics and nutrient cycling, discovering and cataloguing biodiversity through taxonomy and genetics, and describing the foraging behaviour of top predators. Such studies provide the scientific foundation for planning and designing management interventions, while more applied research assesses the effectiveness of interventions such as MPAs, through targeted studies.

As such, Oceans and Coasts is a primary source of ocean data collection in South Africa and in regions that influence environmental conditions around the country, such as the Southern Ocean. At-sea platforms, including the research vessels SA *Agulhas II* and RS *Algoa*, together with a range of autonomous instruments, are central to these efforts. These offshore observations are complemented by top-predator, coastal, shallow-water and estuarine science programmes employing diverse methods, including seabird counts, animal telemetry, biodiversity transects, visual imagery, and sediment sampling. Collectively, these activities, often undertaken in partnership with marine research groups from other government departments, South African universities, and international organisations, contribute to South Africa’s extensive ocean observation and data resources.

Vast quantities of ocean data generated by OC Research, together with data from numerous other contributors and custodians, are integrated into the department’s Oceans and Coasts Information Management System (OCIMS). Through its models, analytical tools, and visualisation products, OCIMS provides accessible information and decision-support tools for the management and sustainable use of South Africa’s oceans and coasts.

To continue delivering impactful science that informs conservation and sustainable development, it is essential to adopt and develop new and innovative platforms and technologies. Equally important is the development of human capacity through the training and mentoring of staff, interns, students and external

researchers. Both technology and innovation, and training and outreach, are embedded into all OC Research programmes and projects.

The above science and science-related activities are guided by a dedicated Science Plan that was developed (and is regularly reviewed) to support Oceans and Coasts in fulfilling its mandate of managing and conserving South Africa's coastal and marine environment, while addressing the country's regional and international commitments to the conservation and sustainable use of the ocean and its biodiversity. Ratification of the BBNJ Treaty by South Africa will likely require greater dedication to research on the high seas beyond national jurisdiction, which will present

challenges given current budgetary and capacity constraints.

Short reports on the science and science-related activities undertaken by OC Research during 2025, including findings or preliminary findings where applicable, are presented in this year's Annual Science Report. As in previous years, the reports are grouped under the headings Monitoring Programmes, Research Highlights, Science to Policy, Platforms, Technology and Innovation, and Training and Outreach. A list of scientific outputs for the calendar year is also provided at the end, including peer-reviewed publications and other products that reflect both the volume and quality of work accomplished by OC Research in 2025.

The Conductivity-Temperature-Depth (CTD) rosette sampler (left) and a plankton Bongo net (right) are two instruments commonly used by OC Research to collect data on essential ocean variables, seen here on the SA *Agulhas II*. Photo credit: Venecia van Balla.

1. INDICATOR FOR COASTAL EUTROPHICATION ALONG ST HELENA BAY MONITORING LINE

Eutrophication, or excessive macronutrient enrichment, is a recurring phenomenon in the St Helena Bay region. It is primarily driven naturally by upwelling at the Cape Columbine upwelling cell and the influence of river (e.g. the Berg River) plumes draining to the bay at the river mouth (Fig. 1). However, it can be exacerbated by human-derived nutrient inputs, leading to harmful algal blooms (HABs), oxygen depletion, mass mortalities of marine life, and poisoning in humans. The Indicator for Coastal Eutrophication (ICEP) is based on the relative balance between nutrient inputs and the nutrient requirements of marine primary producers (phytoplankton) and is a diagnostic tool for assessing the risk of eutrophication in coastal waters. Here, we present spatial and temporal distributions of nutrient loading of Nitrogen (N-ICEP) and Phosphorus (P-ICEP), relative to dissolved silicate (Si) in summer (February) and winter (August) from 2014 to 2025 along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line (SHBML).

Figure 1. Map of the west coast of South Africa, showing the location of the St Helena Bay monitoring line (SHBML) and the Berg River. Red dots indicate SHBML station positions.

Seawater samples for macronutrient measurements were collected from the CTD rosette during the Integrated Ecosystem Program (IEP) surveys. Samples were analysed using the Flow Injection Auto Analyser (FI-AA) system. The mean macronutrient concentrations for Phosphorus (P), Si, and Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN = Nitrate + Nitrite) in the upper 10 m depths were used to calculate the P-ICEP and N-ICEP loading (based on the Redfield ratio of C:N:P:Si 106:16:1:20, and expressed as mg C d^{-1}). Positive ICEP values (>0) indicate excess DIN and P relative to Si, which favours non-siliceous algal biomass and generally signifies higher eutrophication potential. In contrast, a negative

ICEP value (<0) indicates an excess of Si, suggesting a lower risk of eutrophication and a low likelihood of HABs.

Spatially, we observed an offshore decrease in both N-ICEP and P-ICEP values along the transect, due to advection and diffusion of macronutrients. Seasonally, both N- and P-ICEP values were higher in summer than in winter, due to biological uptake resulting in phytoplankton blooms and external nutrient sources from human activities (Fig. 2). During most years, and at the majority of stations along the transect, both N- and P-ICEP were positive and generally indicative of higher eutrophication potential. At some stations, DIN and P did not exceed Si, as indicated by negative ICEP values, with DIN and P being the limiting nutrients. These negative ICEP values, which characterise lower eutrophication risks, were observed in the summers of 2014 (Fig. 2A) and 2024 (Fig. 2A and B), and the winters of 2024 (Fig. 2D) and 2025 (Fig. 2C and 2D). The ICEP is a valuable indicator to highlight nutrient imbalances that favour eutrophication and HABs in this highly productive upwelling system. This makes the ICEP a useful early-warning tool for identifying periods and areas at higher risk of HABs, hypoxia, and ecosystem impacts that threaten fisheries and coastal livelihoods.

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Figure 2. Spatial distributions of (A) N-ICEP loading in February, (B) P-ICEP loading in February, (C) N-ICEP loading in August, and (D) P-ICEP loading in August, along the SHBML during 2014–2025.

2. CHLOROPHYLL *a* VARIABILITY ON THE WEST AND SOUTH COASTS

Phytoplankton are crucial for a number of key marine processes, such as food web modulation and the cycling of carbon and other nutrients. On the west and south coasts of southern Africa, the Benguela upwelling system and the Agulhas Bank are ecologically and economically significant, as they host productive ecosystems with complex trophic structures that support numerous commercially harvested resources. To monitor productivity levels, an index of chlorophyll *a* (a measure of phytoplankton biomass) is computed by integrating satellite-derived surface values from the coast to the 1 mg m⁻³ contour level further offshore (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Annual average chlorophyll *a* concentration and location of the 1 mg m⁻³ contour (thick line). Thin black lines indicate bathymetric contours for 200, 1000 and 3000 m from the coast to offshore waters.

In general, higher index values are associated with greater phytoplankton biomass and a more productive ecosystem, while lower index values indicate lower biomass and a less productive ecosystem. The highest index values are usually found off Namibia (16–26°S; Fig. 2). However, phytoplankton biomass in that region in 2018 was the lowest since 2013. Although somewhat more elevated in 2019 and 2020, index values have been lower and more variable since 2021. Values were higher between 21–26°S during April–June 2024 but were more elevated north of 21°S during August–November 2024. In contrast, index values between 21–26°S were elevated throughout the first half of 2025, with much lower values during the second half of 2025 throughout the 16–26°S region (Fig. 2). Reduced phytoplankton biomass off Namibia since 2018 is likely associated with reduced upwelling of nutrient-rich waters, driven by a southward shift in upwelling-favourable winds previously reported in the literature.

Persistent uplift and offshore transport of surface waters at Lüderitz (~27°S) is typically associated with very low index values. Elevated values here during the summers of 2020, 2021 and 2024 suggested decreased upwelling,

with lower values implying stronger upwelling in 2022 and 2023. Index values here were generally lower during the summer of 2025, implying slightly increased upwelling compared to 2024.

Along South Africa's west coast (SAWC, 28–34°S), index values are generally elevated around the Namaqualand, Cape Columbine and Cape Peninsula upwelling cells. Off Namaqualand (28.5–30°S), values in 2018 were the highest since 2013. Elevated values in 2022 and 2024 suggested improved productivity, but lower values during 2021 and 2023 reflected less productivity. During 2025, index values in this region were elevated throughout the year, suggesting further enhanced productivity compared to 2024.

Along South Africa's south coast (SASC, 18.5–29°E), index values are generally lower than on the SAWC. During 2013–2024, the highest index values occurred at 22–23°E in March–May 2024 and at 20–21°E in September–October 2024. Low values in 2016 suggested it was the least productive year for the SASC during 2013–2024. During February–May 2025, index values at 21–23°E were higher and extended across a larger area along the coast than in 2024.

The varying productivity trends across the region, i.e. a small but significant long-term increase in chlorophyll *a* off Namibia, and a decrease off the SAWC, appear to have continued over the past year. The SASC trend changed from declining to increasing in 2024. In response to continued declines in upwelling-favourable winds, further reductions in phytoplankton biomass along the west coasts of Namibia and South Africa are expected to negatively impact ecosystem functioning, leading to declines in biomass at higher trophic levels, including zooplankton, fish, and top predators.

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Figure 2. Monthly chlorophyll a indices (1997–2025) for the west coasts of Namibia and South Africa (top panel) and for South Africa's south coast (bottom panel).

3. SURFACE CHLOROPHYLL *a* CONCENTRATIONS ALONG THE ST HELENA BAY MONITORING LINE

St Helena Bay on the west coast of South Africa (Fig. 1) is one of the most productive areas of the Benguela ecosystem and has been the focus of environmental research and monitoring for several decades. It is a retention area, with significantly elevated plankton biomass compared to other areas off South Africa, and an important region for many species such as small pelagic fish, hake, whales, and rock lobster.

Figure 1. Map of mean monthly satellite-derived sea surface temperature during the upwelling season (September to March), illustrating cooler waters typically found inshore and warmer waters offshore. The location of the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line is shown, with stations numbered 1–12 and 21–22.

Along the west coast, southeasterly winds transfer surface waters offshore, resulting in cool, nutrient-rich waters being uplifted to the surface from deeper depths (i.e. upwelling). On a seasonal scale, higher chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*, an index of phytoplankton biomass) coincides with larger amounts of upwelling that occur during October–March each year (the upwelling season). Satellite-derived surface chl *a* illustrates this seasonality, with maxima in spring/early summer (usually October) and during the late summer/autumn months of February and March (Fig. 2). Higher chl *a* is usually associated with greater phytoplankton biomass and a more productive ecosystem, which largely results from the higher nutrient availability in the upper ocean during upwelling. In contrast, lower chl *a* indicates lower phytoplankton biomass and a less productive ecosystem, usually associated with less upwelling and nutrient availability in the upper ocean during late autumn to early spring (April–September) each year. Generally, higher chl *a* occurs close to the coast due to higher nutrient availability in the surface layers and decreases with distance offshore as nutrient availability decreases (Fig. 2).

During 2015, high values ($>20 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) extended ca. 20 km offshore in autumn (March) and late spring/early summer (September–November). Similarly high values ($>20 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) were observed much closer to the coast during 2016–2025. Moderately high chlorophyll *a* values of $10\text{--}20 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ were observed less frequently during 2017–2024, extending a maximum of 25 km offshore. In contrast, such values extended ca. 40 km offshore in March 2016, and ca. 50 km offshore in May and September 2025 (Fig. 2).

Elevated chl *a* ($>5 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) extended ca. 110 km offshore in March 2015 – the farthest offshore extent for such elevated values since March 2010. This may have resulted from enhanced offshore transport of surface waters driven by stronger upwelling-favourable winds. Since then, the farthest offshore extents of values above 5 mg m^{-3} were observed in October–November 2024 (ca. 95 km) and December 2025 (ca. 100 km). In February–March 2016 and in April 2022, such values extended ca. 80 km offshore, but did not exceed 70 km offshore during 2017–2021 or in 2023.

Chl *a* in 2017 was lower overall than in 2016 but remained elevated throughout the year. Generally lower values in 2018 and 2021 suggested a less productive ecosystem during these years. In contrast, higher values during 2019, 2020 and 2022 suggested increased productivity. During 2023 and 2024, chl *a* was higher in January–February and in December, with much lower values during March–November suggesting a much less productive autumn-to-spring period compared to the previous decade. During 2025, chl *a* values exceeded 10 mg m^{-3} from February to July, and in September, indicating a more productive ecosystem in the St Helena Bay region in 2025 compared to the previous two years.

Consistent with previously documented chl *a* trends along the west coast of South Africa (see Report Card 2), concentrations along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line show similar minor long-term declines. While long-term chl *a* trends at larger regional scales (see Report Card 2) may be statistically significant, those observed in smaller, more localised regions of the west coast (e.g. Fig. 2) may not be. This likely reflects spatial differences in phytoplankton responses to small-scale variability in upwelling-favourable winds, highlighting the importance of monitoring at finer spatial scales to better detect trends in localised regions.

Author: Lamont T (OC Research)

Figure 2. Time series of satellite-derived monthly chlorophyll *a* (mg m^{-3}) along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line between September 1997 and December 2025. Contour lines indicate chlorophyll *a* concentrations of 1, 5 and 10 mg m^{-3} .

4. MICROZOOPLANKTON ABUNDANCE IN THE SOUTHERN BENGUELA

Microzooplankton are heterotrophic and mixotrophic (obtaining nourishment through both photosynthesis and heterotrophy, i.e. consuming other plants or animals) planktonic organisms that range in size from 20–200 µm. The group comprises flagellates, radiolarians, foraminiferans, ciliates (including tintinnids), copepod nauplii, and other organisms, and plays a key role in many ecosystem processes. Microzooplankton are primary grazers of marine phytoplankton, are major secondary producers (the intermediary between primary producers and copepods), and are instrumental in nutrient and carbon cycling. Their relatively short life cycles (ranging from one week to a year) and rapid responses to environmental changes allow them to serve as robust indicators in marine ecosystems. Microzooplankton abundance is an Essential Ocean Variable under the Global Ocean Observing System, but little is known about this group’s abundance and impacts in the southern Benguela upwelling system (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Map indicating sampling stations along four Integrated Ecosystem Programme: southern Benguela (IEP:SB) monitoring lines, the KML, NML, SHBML and SML.

The Integrated Ecosystem Program in the southern Benguela (IEP:SB) samples four monitoring lines biannually, namely the Kleinsee (KML), Namaqua (NML), St Helena Bay (SHBML), and Scarborough (SML) Monitoring Lines (Fig. 1). Here, we present data from August (winter) and February (summer) of 2018–2025. Surface microzooplankton abundance at each station was assessed using the FlowCam[®] and VisualSpreadsheet software. Abundance of the most prevalent microzooplankton groups, including naked ciliates (without a shell), tintinnids (with a shell) and copepod nauplii, was calculated for the entire west coast

(Fig. 2A) and separately for each monitoring line (Figs. 2B–D).

Total microzooplankton abundance showed an increase between August 2018 and February 2025, although the trend was statistically non-significant ($p = 0.36$) (Fig. 2A). The largest contributors were various tintinnid species, followed by naked ciliates (Figs. 2B,C). Although summer months usually displayed higher total abundance (except for 2020), no clear seasonal patterns were observed for any of the individual groups (Figs. 2B–D). Somewhat higher abundances in summer were likely due to elevated biomass of phytoplankton, a primary food source for microzooplankton. Peak abundance in February 2023 was due to higher numbers of tintinnids on the KML and NML lines (Fig. 2C). Abundance in August 2022 was 4x greater than in other winter sampling events and coincided with the highest observed abundance of tintinnids (Figs. 2A, C). KML and NML exhibited similar patterns across all three groups, while higher abundances were common for the SHBML (Figs. 2B–D). Sampling along the SML was infrequent but revealed high abundances of ciliates and copepod nauplii in February 2019. These results highlight significant latitudinal variability in microzooplankton abundance within the southern Benguela, and further investigation is required to untangle local spatial patterns and temporal dynamics.

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Figure 2. (A) Total microzooplankton abundance along the west coast, and total abundance along the four IEP monitoring lines (KML, NML, SHBML, and SML) for (B) ciliates, (C) tintinnids, and (D) copepod nauplii.

5. FROM LOCAL SHORES TO GLOBAL STANDARDS: BASELINE PLASTICS SURVEY AT STRANDFONTEIN BEACH

Strandfontein Beach, located at Mitchell’s Plain, Cape Town, is a long-term reference site for monitoring coastal plastic pollution in South Africa. This monitoring forms part of national initiatives and contributes to international commitments under the United Nations (UN) Ocean Decade and the UN International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). Strategically situated on an urban, high-use coastline, the site is representative of mixed land-based and marine-derived litter inputs along the False Bay shoreline.

A standing-stock baseline survey was conducted on 6 October 2025. This shoreline debris assessment provides a high-resolution snapshot of the total density of litter present across different beach zones at a single point in time. All litter items were counted, weighed and, where possible, visually identified. Plastic items were further characterised by polymer type using attenuated total reflectance-Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy, enabling rapid, non-destructive chemical identification. Litter density exhibited a clear cross-shore pattern, reflecting the sorting of debris by wind transport into the dune zone, combined with wave and tidal deposition at the high tide zone, with progressively fewer, but mostly heavier, items retained toward the lower tide lines (Table 1).

Table 1. Abundance and density of litter items within each beach zone.

Beach Zone	No. of items (n)	Items per m ²
Dune Zone	712	28.48
High Tide Strandline	338	13.52
Mid-Intertidal Zone	538	21.52
Low-Intertidal/Swash Zone	11	0.44
TOTAL	1,599	63.96
Plastics only	1,201	48.04

The low-intertidal (swash) zone retains or redeposits heavier, denser items that settle quickly and are less susceptible to wind transport (Fig. 1). In contrast, the dune zone acts as an accumulation area for lighter, wind-transported litter. Of the 1,599 items recorded within the 25 m² survey area, 31.6% could be visibly identified as recognisable objects by people and are referred to here as “identifiable” items (Fig. 2). Non-plastic materials, particularly glass, comprised a substantial proportion of the litter collected, underscoring the importance of non-plastic pollution on beaches. The dominant plastic items were lollipop sticks, bottle caps, food packaging, straws, and rope/net fragments, collectively representing

Figure 1. The percentage (%) contribution of each zone to total litter weight at Strandfontein Beach.

common single-use consumer products and fishing-related materials.

Figure 2. Total identifiable litter items.

The dominant polymer types among the plastic litter items were polypropylene and polyethylene (Fig. 3). These polymers are widely used in consumer products and packaging, and their prevalence is consistent with global observations of coastal plastic pollution. The very high density of plastic items recorded during the survey was driven primarily by lightweight, short-lived consumer plastics. These results provide a baseline against which future changes can be assessed.

Figure 3. Polymer type of plastic litter items collected on Strandfontein Beach. Where polymer identification was not possible, it was classified as “no hits”.

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6. A STANDARDISED APPROACH TO MONITORING BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE COMMUNITIES IN MPAS

Benthic invertebrate communities, particularly sessile and semi-motile organisms such as sponges, cnidarians and echinoderms, are useful for assessing long-term change. Their populations respond measurably to factors such as marine pollution or climate change, within weeks to years. Exploratory research on these communities and their habitats has substantially improved understanding of benthic biodiversity and informed the design of marine protected areas (MPAs). However, few repeat observations from the same locations exist to assess temporal changes in benthic community structure and function. Such long-term data sets are essential for evaluating the impacts of climate change and the effectiveness of protection measures. Monitoring benthic ecosystems through repeated observations is therefore a core function of DFFE Branch: Oceans and Coasts.

We developed a cost-effective, non-destructive, standardised protocol for monitoring sessile and semi-motile benthic invertebrate communities within South Africa’s MPAs. Briefly, the protocol is as follows:

(1) Design of a GIS grid overlaying inshore areas (15–100 m depth) to ensure comparable numbers and sizes of stations (dependent on total size of sampling area) across depth bins (Fig. 1A). To minimise bias, stations are selected randomly, and at least 10% of stations per depth bin are sampled to ensure representative coverage of the benthos.

(2) Deployment of a drop camera from a small boat (Fig. 1B), enabling sampling at greater depths than diving (limited to 30 m depth), and allowing easy access to shallow areas where larger research vessels are unsuitable. This approach is considerably more cost effective than alternative underwater imaging platforms such as Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) or Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), requiring minimal personnel (a skipper, winch operator and scribe).

(3) At each station, the drop camera is deployed for 60 seconds, repeated 20–30 times depending on station size. Detailed metadata sheets ensure accurate records of operations (e.g. bottom times), while a temperature logger mounted on the camera frame enables correlation with environmental conditions.

(4) Data are collected as measurable photoquadrats (Fig. 2) that can be annotated for species and substrate classification using the open-source Benthic Image

Figure 1. (A) Map with grid overlaying the Olifantsbos area inside Table Mountain National Park MPA. Randomly selected stations (250 x 250 m in size) are shown by black circles. (B) The drop camera deployed via an adaptable winch system from a small boat. (C) BIIGLE software used to annotate images.

Indexing and Graphics Labelling Environment (BIIGLE) software (Fig. 1C).

(5) Repeat sampling of stations every 2–3 years.

This protocol allows repeatable, comparable monitoring of benthos across all inshore MPAs in South Africa (see Report Card 7). Its affordability, operational simplicity, and non-destructive approach make it a robust tool for incorporating benthic biodiversity data into MPA management strategies. It can also easily be extended to greater depths by using larger research vessels.

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Figure 2. Selected images of benthic taxa, in the form of photoquadrats from the drop camera, in the Table Mountain National Park and Robben Island MPAs.

7. FIRST LONG-TERM MONITORING OBSERVATIONS OF THE BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE COMMUNITY IN THE ROBBERN ISLAND MPA

Long-term temperature monitoring captures the local variability and temperature extremes experienced by marine organisms in their natural microhabitats. Such data can be used in physiological research to improve experimental designs and predictions of how marine organisms will fare with changing climatic conditions. This study reports on microhabitat temperatures that were obtained through the deployment of temperature loggers in intertidal rockpools.

Many marine protected areas (MPAs) in South Africa were originally established with fisheries management or species conservation as their primary goals. However, effective MPA management requires an ecosystem-based approach that encompasses all components of biodiversity, including non-target taxa such as sessile and semi-motile benthic invertebrates. The benthic zone provides crucial habitat and food resources for a range of ecologically and economically important species. Conservation efforts can be strengthened by better descriptions of the benthic environment and an improved understanding of how benthic biota changes over time. This requires the establishment of long-term monitoring programmes within MPAs to assess climate-driven changes. Sessile and semi-motile benthic invertebrates are particularly valuable indicators of long-term change, as their populations respond measurably to pressures such as marine pollution and climate change over weeks to years. Gazetted in 2019, Robben Island MPA (Fig. 1) is one of three new MPAs managed by SANParks, established primarily to protect the Island's endangered seabird populations.

Figure 1. A grid of 500 x 500 m locations (grey blocks) overlaying the inshore region of Robben Island MPA. Red blocks indicate randomly selected sampling locations. Vessel traffic regions (pink, purple, and light blue shading) were excluded from the survey design.

Using a non-destructive drop camera system and a randomised sampling design, we established small-scale long-term monitoring of macro-benthic marine invertebrates over the 15–100 m depth range. In 2025, a total of 50 stations (30 camera drops in each red block, Fig. 1) were sampled across three depth bins: 15–30 m, 31–65 m and 66–100 m.

Figure 2. (A) Mean number of individuals and (B) Mean occurrence of substrate type across depth bins.

Preliminary results indicate the MPA supports a rich and diverse array of benthos (Fig. 2A) with mixed habitat types (rocks, boulders, patches of sand, and mud/silt covering boulders in the deeper reaches) (Fig. 2B). Boulders and rocks (hard substrata) appear to be preferred habitats, which may explain the high diversity and abundance of benthos across the sampling area. Brachiopods and molluscs were the dominant taxa across all depth strata (Fig. 2A), with dense mussel beds covering boulders and winkles spread across sandy patches. Cape urchins, aggregations of brittle stars, and a variety of starfish, feather-stars and sea cucumbers accounted for the high numbers of echinoderms. Cnidarians were among the dominant taxa at all depths, consisting mainly of hard corals, solitary stony corals, and two anemone species (one occupying boulders and the other occupying sandy patches along with sea pens). Encrusting and ball sponges were similarly abundant.

These baseline observations suggest that the benthic communities within the MPA provide important habitat and food resources for fish assemblages and, indirectly, the island's endangered seabird populations. Future work should include repeat surveys at 2–3-year intervals and analyses to explore environmental correlations.

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8. THE RESILIENCE OF CROWNED CORMORANTS AMIDST GENERAL SEABIRD DECLINE

The crowned cormorant *Microcarbo coronata* is endemic to the Benguela ecosystem where they are known to have bred at 72 localities between Bird Rock Platform in central Namibia and on South Africa's south coast. Crowned cormorants breed along the coast and on coastal islands, nesting on elevated platforms, trees or abandoned buildings (Fig. 1). The population is small (<6,000 mature individuals), and in 2015 the species was assessed as Near Threatened by the IUCN in both Namibia and South Africa. Here we report long-term trends in counts of crowned cormorant breeding pairs and discuss their implications.

Figure 1. Breeding crowned cormorants at Malgas Island.

The highest number of breeding pairs recorded across breeding colonies was 2,665 during 1977–1981, declining slightly to 2,345 during 1995–2006 (Fig. 2). Data for Namibia were not available during 2008–2012, when numbers in South Africa increased from 1,327 to 1,908 breeding pairs. Total counts during the time series peaked at 2,748 in 2013–2017, before declining slightly to 2,558 pairs in 2018–2022. Subsequently, there was a marked decline to 2,195 in 2022–2025, with a 47% to 53% split in the breeding population between Namibia and South Africa, respectively. In South Africa, the recent declines were manifest as a 30% decrease in the number of breeding pairs over five years and a 17% decrease over three generations (Fig. 3), with only nine localities sustaining ≥ 100 pairs since 2018.

Despite the declines, the crowned cormorant population has exhibited demographic stability compared to some other local seabird populations, which have shown unprecedented declines due to overfishing and climate change. Their decline has not been nearly as severe as those of the sympatric bank cormorant *Phalacrocorax neglectus*, Cape cormorant *Phalacrocorax capensis* (both Endangered), and African penguin *Spheniscus demersus* (Critically Endangered).

The diet of the crowned cormorant differs significantly from that of Cape cormorants, which feed on commercially important small pelagic fish, especially anchovy and sardines. Crowned cormorants are shallow benthic foragers that primarily target klipfish, pipefish, gobies, blennies and soles. Some crustaceans, molluscs and polychaetes have also been observed in their diet. In general, their prey species are of no commercial interest.

Figure 2. The breeding population size of the crowned cormorant across its distributional range in the Benguela Ecosystem.

The apparent resilience of the crowned cormorant population may therefore result from its specialised near-shore foraging strategy, which reduces direct competition with commercial fisheries. However, the species is by no means immune to threats. Important stressors to crowned cormorants include their sensitivity to human disturbance at breeding sites, loss of breeding habitat, and mortality resulting from oiling, disease and incorporation of human debris into nests. Reduced reproductive success or immature survival due to flooding of low-lying nests during storms, egg loss and predation on chicks and fledglings by natural predators are other factors.

Figure 3. Number of crowned cormorant breeding pairs counted in South Africa since 1985.

Management priorities should include avoiding human disturbance during breeding and protecting known feeding areas during this period. Continued monitoring at all known nesting sites is important to detect further declines.

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9. TEMPORAL VARIABILITY AND CHANGES IN FIN WHALE SONG CHARACTERISTICS OFF THE WEST COAST OF SOUTH AFRICA

Cetaceans are sensitive to environmental change and are thus excellent ocean basin sentinel species. The fin whale *Balaenoptera physalus* is a species of baleen whale (possessing baleen plates in its mouth to filter plankton for food) that undertakes summer high latitude to winter low latitude migrations. They are classified as Vulnerable by the International Union for Conservation of Nature. Information on the temporal variability and song evolution of fin whale calls can provide insight into this elusive species' ecology and migratory behaviour. Here, we report on the temporal occurrence and song characteristics of fin whales, as determined from passive acoustic monitoring data collected off the west coast of South Africa (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Bathymetry map with Autonomous Acoustic Recorder (AAR) locations off the west coast of South Africa, with AAR 1 indicated by the green dot, AARs 2, 3 and 5 by pink dots, and AAR 4 by the blue dot.

To assess and monitor basin-scale oceanographic variability and the consequent responses of biological communities, DFFE leads annual multi-disciplinary data collections along the South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation Basin-wide Array (SAMBA) transect. This transect extends south-westward from the west coast of South Africa across the continental shelf, before continuing westward along 34.5°S from the shelf edge across the Cape Basin to 0°E. Between 2014 and 2016, data were obtained using Autonomous Underwater Recorders (AARs) for Acoustic Listening Model 2 instruments at four locations (AAR1–AAR4; Fig. 1). A SoundTrap ST600 HF was used in 2023–2024 at a fifth location (AAR5).

Throughout both measurement periods, fin whale socialising calls (20 Hz and accompanying 99 Hz pulses) were the main vocalisations detected. Only one 40 Hz feeding call was detected in 2024, indicating that these whales displayed mainly social, rather than feeding, behaviour. Fin whale calls occurred most frequently in austral winter and were rare in summer, suggesting a seasonal migratory presence, apart from the few individuals or groups that were detected year-round (Fig. 2). Notably, their presence in autumn appears to have

Figure 2. Monthly presence of fin whale calls per year.

increased over time, such that peak call occurrence was recorded in autumn rather than winter in 2024.

Peak frequency and duration of 20 Hz pulses decreased over time (Fig. 3a,b), as did peak frequency of 99 Hz pulses, although their duration showed an increasing trend (Fig. 3c,d). This shift in song characteristics needs further investigation. Nevertheless, our study provides the first temporal overview of fin whale song characteristics off the west coast of South Africa. The absence of feeding calls, along with the winter-dominated seasonal presence, suggests that the region is an important overwintering and breeding ground for fin whales. The increase in autumn detection suggests a shift in the timing of migratory behaviour. Our findings highlight the importance of sustained long-term observations to identify potential responses or adaptations of cetaceans to environmental variations, including global warming and increased noise pollution.

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Figure 3. Median difference in peak frequency (Hz) and signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR)-adjusted mean difference in call duration (s) for 20 Hz pulses (A,B), and 99 Hz pulses (C,D) of fin whale calls between 2014–2016 and 2023–2024.

10. LONG-TERM VARIABILITY IN BOTTOM TEMPERATURE ON THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS SHELF

Despite their small size, the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) provide crucial breeding habitat for vast populations of marine mammals and seabirds that depend strongly on the ambient oceanographic conditions at and around the islands. While annual relief voyages to resupply the research base only allow hydrographic data collection during April/May each year, two moorings on the inter-island shelf (Fig. 1) have been providing continuous measurements of bottom temperature since 2014.

Figure 1. Map of the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) showing bathymetry on the PEI shelf. Mooring positions M1 and M2 are shown as black dots. White shading indicates no data.

Mooring M1 (174 m depth) is shallower than M2 (216 m depth) and thus, bottom temperatures at M2 are ca. 0.7°C cooler than those at M1 (Fig. 2). Overall lower temperatures (below the long-term mean) during 2014–2017 reflected more frequent northward meanders of the southern branch of the sub-Antarctic Front (S-SAF; Fig. 2). Since 2018, temperatures have been generally elevated (above the long-term mean), indicating a more southerly location of the S-SAF. Linear temperature increases at M1 and M2 were 1.06 and 0.84°C decade⁻¹, respectively. The number of large cooling events (with temperatures below the long-term mean for longer than two days at a time) has decreased from five events in 2021 to two in 2022, three in 2023, and one in 2024 (Fig. 2). The 23 February–12 April 2024 cooling event occurred during interaction of two cyclonic eddies (labelled C) with the PEIs (Fig. 3a). Here, cooling was minimal, up to 0.46°C at M2, and up to 0.25°C at M1 (Fig. 2). Notably, temperatures were warmer on average during 2024–2025 (by 1.1°C at M1 and 0.7°C at M2) than in previous years, due to the S-SAF being located south of the PEIs. Two substantial warming events occurred, from 16 June to 14 September 2024, and from 2 March to 24 April 2025, resulting in the highest bottom temperatures over the past eleven years. Here, maximum temperatures exceeded 7.0°C at M1 and 6.0°C at M2 (Fig. 2). For the June–September 2024 event, maximum warming occurred ca. 4 July, when an anticyclonic eddy (labelled A) interacted with the PEIs, likely advecting

Figure 3. Daily sea surface height (m) on (a) 10 March 2024 and (b) 16 Jun 2024, and (c) 22 April 2025. The middle (M-SAF; solid black contour) and southern (S-SAF; dashed black contour) branches of the sub-Antarctic Front are shown.

warmer sub-Antarctic surface water (SASW) onto the shelf (Fig. 3b). Although a large cyclonic eddy (labelled C) interacted with the PEIs during the March–April 2025 event, it also appeared to advect warmer SASW onto the shelf, as the S-SAF was south of the PEIs (Fig. 3c).

Temperature variations may affect distances that seabirds and marine mammals must travel from the islands to find food. This has consequences for time and energy spent foraging, for the survival of young that depend on foraging adults, and ultimately for the reproductive success and abundance trends of these populations. Substantially warmer conditions in 2024–2025 may mean less food availability at the PEIs, and hence longer travel times for seabirds and marine mammals that breed there.

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Figure 2. Daily mean bottom temperature (°C) at moorings M1 (red) and M2 (blue). Dashed lines indicate measurements while solid lines show low-pass filtered values with a 30-day cut-off. Horizontal dotted lines show mean temperatures while diagonal lines show long-term trends for each time series (2014–2025). Grey shading highlights major warming and cooling events during 2014–2025.

11. LONG-TERM OBSERVATIONS OF CURRENTS ON THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS SHELF

The Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) are a remote island archipelago in the sub-Antarctic zone of the Southern Ocean. They provide crucial breeding habitat for vast populations of seabirds and marine mammals. It is well-known that there are strong links between the oceanography and biological communities at the PEIs, but observations have been largely limited to periods coinciding with annual relief voyages in April–May. To contribute to long-term oceanographic observations, two moorings deployed on the inter-island shelf (Fig. 1) have been providing continuous measurements of water column current speed and direction since April 2014.

Figure 1. Map of the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) showing bathymetry on the PEI shelf. Mooring positions M1 and M2 are shown as black dots. White shading indicates no data.

The eastward-flowing Antarctic Circumpolar Current results in much stronger zonal (east/west) than meridional (north/south) flow at the PEIs. During 2014–2025, daily mean current speeds at mooring M1 ranged from 0.01 to 50.90 cm s^{-1} , and those at M2 from 0.03 to 67.32 cm s^{-1} . A Taylor column structure, which is a stationary anticyclonic (anticlockwise) circulation over the shelf, is indicated by westerly flow in the bottom waters at M2 (Fig. 2). This bottom westerly flow is persistent but can be enhanced or interrupted when fronts or mesoscale eddies interact with the shelf. Retention of nutrients and biota by the Taylor column enhances productivity on the shelf, accounting for high concentrations of marine biota at the PEIs.

During the cooling event from 23 February to 12 April 2024 (see Report Card 10, Fig. 3a), currents changed from easterly to westerly as cyclonic (clockwise) eddies interacted with the PEI shelf (Fig. 2). Similar flow direction changes occurred during the March–April 2025 warming event (Fig. 2). While the anticyclonic (anticlockwise) eddy (labelled A) that initiated the June–September 2024 warming event (see Report Card 10, Fig. 3b) dissipated by 21 July (Fig. 3), the warming continued for a further 56 days. The orientation of a frontal meander to the west and formation of a cyclonic eddy (labelled C) to the east of the PEIs (Fig. 3) likely aided retention of the warmer waters from the anticyclonic eddy in the PEI region, resulting in the prolonged warming.

Figure 3. Daily sea surface height (m) on (a) 4 July 2024, (b) 11 July 2024, and (c) 21 July 2024. The middle (M-SAF; solid black contour) and southern (S-SAF; dashed black contour) branches of the sub-Antarctic Front are shown.

Changes in the direction of current flow may influence the distribution of preferred prey, and consequently, the feeding patterns of seabirds and marine mammals breeding at the PEIs. Detailed comparisons between current patterns and the feeding behaviour, diet, and reproductive performance of selected predators are required to evaluate the impact of these changing flow dynamics on top predators. To date, no clear long-term trends in current speed or direction have been detected on the PEI shelf. However, the available time series are likely too short to adequately resolve such trends. It is thus crucial to maintain and extend these observations to establish time series of sufficient length to accurately detect long-term changes.

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Figure 2. Daily mean zonal (east/west) and meridional (north/south) current components (cm s⁻¹) at (a) M1 and (b) M2 during 2014–2025. Positive values denote easterly and northerly flow; negative values denote westerly and southerly flow. Red boxes highlight warming events during June–September 2024 and March–April 2025, while the black box highlights a cooling event during February–April 2024.

12. WARMING AND WEAKER CURRENTS AROUND THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS OVER THE PAST FIVE YEARS

The Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) are a remote island archipelago in the sub-Antarctic zone of the Southern Ocean. They provide crucial breeding habitat for vast populations of seabirds and marine mammals. It is well-known that there are strong links between the oceanography and biological communities at the PEIs, but observations have been largely limited to periods coinciding with annual relief voyages in April–May. To contribute to long-term oceanographic observations, two moorings deployed on the inter-island shelf (Fig. 1) have been providing continuous measurements of water column current speed and direction since April 2014.

Figure 1. Bathymetry map of the Prince Edward Islands. M-SAF denotes the middle branch of the sub-Antarctic Front, S-SAF the southern branch of the sub-Antarctic Front, and N-APF is the northern branch of the Antarctic Polar Front.

Here, we expand the study to highlight the seasonal and spatial changes in SST and surface current speeds that have taken place around the PEIs over the past five years. To do this, we have computed the bias (difference) between the updated climatological means, including new data until 2025 and the previous monthly climatological means computed in 2020. Positive biases indicate higher SSTs and current speeds, while negative biases indicate lower SSTs and current speeds in the 2025 climatological means.

Figure 2 illustrates widespread positive SST biases throughout the year across most of the region. This indicates that the ocean environment surrounding the PEIs has warmed over the past five years. The largest positive biases, up to 0.13°C , occurred north of the PEIs, with the strongest warming in summer and early autumn (December–March). Less warming (up to 0.09°C) took place during the remaining months, with October showing the least warming ($<0.06^{\circ}\text{C}$). Negative biases indicating cooling over the past five years were evident mainly south of the PEIs, except in May and June, when some cooling was evident in the northern part of the region (Fig. 2). The strongest cooling, by as much as 0.05°C , took place in September and October.

Surface current speed biases (Fig. 3) showed the reverse spatial pattern, with a general weakening of current speeds to the north of the PEIs and strengthening to the south. In the southwestern part of the region, current speeds increased by as much as 0.02 m s^{-1} in most months, with the strongest increases (up to 0.03 m s^{-1})

occurring in November. The decreases (up to 0.02 m s^{-1} slower) in surface current speed have been less pronounced than the current speed increases.

Widespread warming observed from reanalysis products (Fig. 2) agrees with the warming evident from moored observations on the shelf (see Report Card 10, Fig. 2). This reflects the influence of the surrounding ocean on environmental conditions over the PEI shelf. The general weakening of current speeds (Fig. 3) is not reflected in the moored observations on the shelf (see Report Card 11, Fig. 2) due to the much higher variability of current speeds on the shelf.

The warming and weaker surface current speeds to the north of the PEIs, with cooling and stronger surface currents to the south, appears to be the result of a southward shift in the location of the southern branch of the sub-Antarctic Front (S-SAF). This frontal shift, also described in Report Cards 10 and 11, is likely driven by larger-scale changes in the position and intensity of the westerly wind belt in the Southern Ocean.

The shift can have substantial impacts on the PEIs and its top predator populations. For example, wandering albatrosses *Diomedea exulans*, which typically travel northward from the PEIs to forage along the S-SAF, may need to travel southward instead. The overall warmer conditions on the PEI shelf may result in a reduction of food availability for some species that usually forage nearshore, such as the gentoo penguin *Pygoscelis papua*. On the other hand, the frontal shift may cause increased presence over the PEI shelf of pelagic prey items that are usually found further offshore.

Top predators do not always respond as expected to environmental changes. For example, studies in mainland South Africa have described how some African penguins *Spheniscus demersus* continued to forage in areas of reduced food availability, despite more suitable foraging conditions elsewhere along the coast. Ongoing research is needed to determine if and how the PEI top predator populations alter their foraging behaviour and diet in response to the changing environment around the PEIs.

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Figure 2. Sea surface temperature bias ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) between the climatological periods of 1981–2025 and 1981–2020.

Figure 3. Surface current speed bias (m s^{-1}) between the climatological periods of 1993–2025 and 1993–2020.

13. SURFACE NUTRIENT DISTRIBUTIONS AROUND GOUGH ISLAND

Gough Island (GI) is a sub-Antarctic island in the South Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 1), where interactions between island topography and the surrounding circulation strongly influence surface biogeochemistry. Nutrient distributions in the upper ocean reflect a balance between physical supply, biological uptake, and regeneration. Surface nutrient ratios therefore provide key insights into phytoplankton productivity, nutrient limitation, and ecosystem structure in this dynamic island-influenced environment.

Figure 1. Map showing the sampling track (blue line) and sampled stations (red dots) to the north (N), east (E), south (S), and west (W) of Gough Island.

Seawater samples were collected underway from ca. 7 m depth during the GI 2025 cruise. Conical tubes were rinsed three times prior to collection of the 50 ml samples, which were then immediately stored in a -80°C freezer. Samples were defrosted ashore and analysed using the SEAL analytical AA500 autoanalyzer to determine concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^-), nitrite (NO_2^-), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and silicate (SiO_4^{4-}).

A total of 28 surface samples collected around GI showed moderate concentrations of dissolved inorganic nitrogen ($\text{DIN} = \text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$), PO_4^{3-} , and SiO_4^{4-} . DIN ranged from 3.57 to 7.87 μM (mean \pm SD: $6.68 \pm 1.10 \mu\text{M}$), while PO_4^{3-} varied between 0.34 and 0.62 μM (mean \pm SD: $0.49 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{M}$) (Fig. 2A, B). Silicate concentrations were relatively low, spanning 0.50–1.64 μM (mean \pm SD: $1.20 \pm 0.28 \mu\text{M}$) (Fig. 2C). On average, nutrient ratios were low toward the south and west of the island, with higher values toward the north and east (Fig. 2D–F). High ratios of S:DIN and S:P were observed at a single station to the southwest of the island (Fig. 2D, F), while high DIN:P ratios were uniformly distributed over a much larger area to the north and east of the island.

Spatial variability in ratios was modest, implying broadly homogeneous surface nutrient ratios around the island at the time of sampling.

Figure 2. Distribution of surface nutrients and nutrient ratios around the GI for (A) DIN, (B) PO_4^{3-} , (C) SiO_4^{4-} , (D) S:DIN, (E) DIN:P, (F) S:P.

The surface nutrient ratios observed around GI suggest a transition toward nitrogen limitation, as indicated by N:P values below the expected Redfield ratio of 16:1. Such N:P values are observed once regenerated nitrogen becomes the dominant DIN source. In the highly energetic oceanographic setting of the GI, frontal interactions, island-wake dynamics, and episodic vertical mixing are likely to promote short, intense productivity events. During such pulses, rapid diatom growth can efficiently utilise available SiO_4^{4-} , leading to the exhaustion of silica, relative to nitrogen. This explains the low Si:DIN ratios observed (Fig. 2D).

These surface nutrient ratio patterns are commonly observed in sub-Antarctic island environments after phytoplankton bloom events. It favours non-diatom phytoplankton assemblages, which are better adapted to low silicate conditions. This varying nutrient availability reinforces the transient and spatially variable nature of phytoplankton productivity around the Gough Island.

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14. VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION OF NUTRIENTS AROUND GOUGH ISLAND

The vertical distribution of nutrients around Gough Island reflects the combined influence of island-ocean interactions, frontal activity, and water-column stratification, which characterise sub-Antarctic environments. These processes can modify nutrient supply to the upper ocean by enhancing mixing, altering circulation pathways, and stimulating episodic biological production.

During the Gough Island 2025 expedition aboard the SA *Agulhas II*, ship-based hydrographic sampling was conducted using discrete-depth nutrient measurements to characterise vertical gradients in nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, and silicate (Fig. 1). Assessing the vertical structure of these nutrients provides important insight into patterns of nutrient limitation and the balance between physical forcing and biological uptake in the South Atlantic sector of the Southern Ocean.

Figure 1. Map of the Gough Island sampling station locations, grouped into two regimes: downstream (stations 1, 1a, 2, 10, 2 and 3) and upstream (stations 4–9). Blue circles with black outlines denote individual station positions, with station numbers labelled.

Stations located near the island exhibited the strongest vertical gradients in nutrient concentrations, characterised by pronounced surface depletion of nitrate and silicate and enhanced subsurface concentrations (Fig. 2). Downstream stations showed similarly low surface nutrient concentrations but with smoother vertical transitions and reduced subsurface variability. In contrast, upstream stations displayed more uniform vertical nutrient distributions, with comparatively higher surface concentrations and weaker vertical gradients. Nitrite was largely confined to the upper water column across all station groups, with a deeper signal observed only at Station 4.

To our interpretation, the spatial patterns in nutrients most likely reflect island-wake processes, combined with changes that occur as water flows past the island. The strong vertical gradients at near-island stations are consistent with increased biological uptake and

Figure 2. Vertical sections of nutrient concentrations around Gough Island showing (A) nitrate (NO_3^-), (B) nitrite (NO_2^-), (C) phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), and (D) silicate (SiO_4^{4-}). Black dots indicate individual discrete samples for stations 1 to 10.

recycling, driven by local mixing and enhanced productivity around Gough Island.

Downstream stations retained the signature of upstream nutrient drawdown, indicating the advection of biologically modified waters away from the island with limited vertical resupply. In contrast, the more uniform profiles at upstream stations likely reflect background sub-Antarctic conditions prior to island influence. The confinement of nitrite to shallow depths, particularly near the island, further supports the interpretation of active regenerated production and nitrification within the upper water column. Collectively, these patterns indicate that Gough Island locally modifies nutrient dynamics, superimposing a distinct island effect on the broader regional nutrient gradients.

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15. DISTRIBUTION AND FLUXES OF DISSOLVED TRACE METAL IRON AROUND GOUGH ISLAND

Dissolved iron (DFe) plays a fundamental role in regulating marine biogeochemical cycles, ecosystem productivity, and ocean-atmosphere carbon exchange (via the biological carbon pump). Its large-scale distribution in the Southern Ocean is governed by a balance between external inputs (including atmospheric deposition, riverine discharge, sedimentary release and ice melt) and internal removal processes (e.g. biological uptake, precipitation and coagulation, abiotic scavenging onto sinking particles), and physical transport. Vertical fluxes driven by winter entrainment, upwelling and mixing can supply DFe from subsurface reservoirs to the euphotic zone or mixed layer depth, thereby sustaining primary productivity. Horizontal fluxes associated with advection and diffusion transport further redistribute DFe across ocean basins and frontal systems.

Here we quantify the relative contribution of these DFe fluxes to the upper surface mixed layer depth around Gough Island (GI). Seawater samples for DFe measurements were collected during the GI 2024 cruise, using a trace-clean GEOTRACES CTD rosette, and analysed using Agilent Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). See [Report Card 14](#), Figure 1, for upstream and downstream sampling station locations; these were the same as during the GI 2025 cruise, excluding Station 1a.

Our results show that horizontal diffusion flux is the dominant physical process both upstream and downstream of the island, with values ranging from $\sim 10^5$ – 10^6 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1). This reflects strong lateral DFe gradients and large effective diffusivities, indicating that mesoscale–sub-mesoscale stirring is the primary mechanism redistributing DFe along the transect. Horizontal advection is secondary but non-negligible.

Upstream, advective fluxes are modest (~ 10 – 30 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$), comparable to or slightly exceeding estimated biological iron (Fe) demand (typical Southern Ocean biological Fe demand is ~ 1 – 50 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$). Downstream, stronger currents and deeper mixed layers amplify advective transport to $\sim 10^3$ – 10^4 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, making advection an important contributor to the mixed-layer Fe inventory. In contrast, vertical advection and vertical diffusion are small (typically $|F| < 0.05$ $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) and often change sign (negative

fluxes indicate a loss due to sinking particles and scavenging). This indicates a weak and spatially variable vertical exchange across the mixed-layer base. Their net contribution to surface Fe supply is minor compared with horizontal processes. Entrainment provides a substantial episodic vertical input (10^3 – 10^4 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$), particularly downstream, where deeper mixed layers enhance incorporation of subsurface Fe. However, even entrainment is generally smaller than horizontal diffusion (Fig. 1). Overall, our results show that horizontal diffusion is the primary supply process, with advection and entrainment acting as secondary, spatially heterogeneous sources, while vertical diffusive and advective fluxes play a comparatively minor role.

In this naturally iron-fertilised region, dFe availability regulates phytoplankton biomass and species composition, which in turn influences food for zooplankton and higher trophic levels. Any changes in ocean circulation, stratification or Fe inputs can alter primary production and food-web dynamics. Quantifying dFe supply to the mixed layer is therefore essential for understanding and predicting ecosystem productivity, trophic transfer efficiency, and the vulnerability of sub-Antarctic marine ecosystems to future climate change.

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Figure 1. Bar plots showing the daily rates of dFe fluxes ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) at stations (A) upstream and (B) downstream of GI, resulting from H_{adv} = horizontal advection, H_{diff} = horizontal diffusion, V_{adv} = vertical advection, V_{diff} = vertical diffusion, and Entr = winter entrainment.

16. THE TINY PLANKTON OF THE SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN

Gough Island lies midway between South Africa and South America in the South Atlantic Ocean. The island is located near the South Subtropical Convergence frontal zone and is influenced by warmer, low-nutrient waters of the northern subtropical gyre and cooler, high-nutrient sub-Antarctic waters to the south. Mixing of these water masses leads to enhanced nutrient concentrations and primary production. Picophytoplankton (0.2-2 μm in size) are the smallest component of the primary producer community and play a vital role in regulating climate and supporting marine food chains. However, our understanding of these tiny plankton groups remains limited, particularly in this remote region of the South Atlantic.

Figure 1. Map showing the location of 11 CTD sampling stations surrounding Gough Island (grey area).

Samples for picophytoplankton analysis were collected at stations surrounding Gough Island during a survey aboard the SA *Agulhas II* in 2025 (Fig. 1). At each station, seawater was collected using a CTD at two depths: the surface and the maximum fluorescence layer (fmax) between 20 and 120 m. The collected seawater was prefiltered through a 200 μm mesh sieve. Three sub-samples per depth were collected, preserved and stored frozen until analysis using a flow cytometer.

Synechococcus was the dominant picophytoplankton group co-occurring with *Prochlorococcus* and picoeukaryotes at all stations, with mean total abundances of 121,2 and 80,4 thousand cells mL^{-1} at the surface and fmax, respectively (Fig. 2). Measures of surface abundance (Fig. 3) showed that the highest abundance of picophytoplankton was found at station AMO1668 located at ca. 41°S upstream of the island (Fig. 1).

Figure 2. The total abundance (cells mL^{-1}) of picophytoplankton groups (a) at the surface and (b) at the fmax. SYN = *Synechococcus*, PRO = *Prochlorococcus* and PICO = picoeukaryotes.

Lower abundances were observed at stations surrounding the island (Fig. 3). *Synechococcus* abundance (6,000 cells mL^{-1}) was three times higher than that of *Prochlorococcus* (2,000 cells mL^{-1}) (Fig. 3a and b) and this is likely influenced by the oceanic mixing of nutrients, light availability and temperature in the South Atlantic. *Synechococcus* is adapted to cooler and more variable light and nutrient conditions that favours phytoplankton growth, which may provide a competitive advantage in this dynamic system. The co-occurrence of *Prochlorococcus* and picoeukaryotes further suggests that small-scale variability in light, nutrients, and water mass structure promotes niche differentiation within the picophytoplankton community. Together, these patterns show how ocean mixing and shifting water conditions shape tiny plankton communities in the South Atlantic.

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Figure 3. Surface abundance (cells per mL^{-1}) of (a) *Synechococcus*, (b) *Prochlorococcus* and (c) picoeukaryotes sampled around Gough Island. Black dots represent stations sampled.

17. PICOPHYTOPLANKTON COMMUNITIES IN THE SOUTHERN BENGUELA DURING SUMMER AND WINTER

The southern Benguela is strongly influenced by seasonal upwelling events that transport cold, nutrient-rich waters to the surface. These events, together with subsequent relaxation periods of weak or no upwelling, strongly influence the variability, composition, and distribution of plankton communities. Within these communities, picophytoplankton constitute the smallest size class (<3 μm) and are dominated by groups such as *Prochlorococcus*, *Synechococcus*, and picoeukaryotes. These micro-organisms play a key role in marine primary production, particularly under variable nutrient conditions. This study compares picophytoplankton communities during summer (February 2024), when upwelling is more frequent, and winter (August 2024), when upwelling is less frequent, using data collected within the Integrated Ecosystem Programme (IEP).

Figure 1. Map showing the southern Benguela off the west coast of South Africa. The St Helena Bay Monitoring Line stations are shown as black dots and the colour shading indicates *Synechococcus* abundance (cells mL^{-1}) in February 2024.

Seawater samples were collected from the surface and depth of maximum fluorescence (Fmax) at each station along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line (Fig. 1), using Niskin bottles mounted on a CTD rosette. Water samples were prefiltered through a 200 μm pore-size sieve, and subsamples ($3 \times 2 \text{ mL}$) were then pipetted into cryovials, fixed with glutaraldehyde (0.25% final concentration), and stored at -80°C . Analyses were conducted using a BD FACSymphony A1 flow cytometer equipped with a red laser (670/30 nm) and a yellow-green laser (585/15 nm).

Picoeukaryotes exhibited higher abundance at the depth of Fmax during summer but were more dominant at the surface during winter (Fig. 2a). In contrast, *Synechococcus* species were consistently more dominant at the surface than at the depth of Fmax during both summer and winter (Fig. 2b). Similarly, *Prochlorococcus* species were dominant at the surface in both seasons (Fig. 2c).

Marked seasonal differences in picophytoplankton cell abundances were likely associated with the transition from newly upwelled nutrient-rich waters during summer to more retentive, lower-nutrient conditions during winter, when smaller organisms have a competitive advantage over larger taxa such as diatoms. Elevated surface abundances of picoeukaryotes during winter suggest that these organisms are better adapted to the lower nutrient conditions that characterise this period (Fig. 2a). *Prochlorococcus* dominated the picophytoplankton community in terms of abundance during both surveys, despite having the smallest cell

Figure 2. Abundance of (a) Picoeukaryotes, (b) *Synechococcus* and (c) *Prochlorococcus* at the surface and at the depth of maximum fluorescence (Fmax) during February and August 2024.

size among the groups (Fig. 2c). *Prochlorococcus* dominance may reflect their ability to adapt to varying environmental factors such as light availability, temperature, and nutrient concentrations, as well as their capacity for faster reproduction compared to *Synechococcus* and the picoeukaryotes.

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18. SURFACE NUTRIENT RATIOS ALONG THE SAMBA MONITORING LINE DURING EARLY SPRING 2025

The South Atlantic oceanic region (Fig. 1) is characterised by low surface nutrient concentrations resulting from strong stratification, weak vertical mixing, and limited lateral nutrient inputs. The primary nutrient supply to the euphotic zone is largely controlled by slow diffusive fluxes, episodic mixing events, and recycling within the microbial loop rather than sustained upwelling. Surface nutrient ratios provide critical insight into biogeochemical functioning and nutrient limitation in such oligotrophic oceanic regions. Ratios among dissolved inorganic nitrogen, phosphorus, and silicate reflect the balance between physical supply processes and biological uptake. They are commonly evaluated relative to canonical Redfield proportions of Nitrogen (N) to Phosphate (P) to Silicate (S), expressed as N:P:Si = 16:1:16. In stratified surface waters, preferential removal of nitrogen often leads to depressed N:P ratios and elevated Si:N or Si:P ratios, influencing phytoplankton community structure and regulating primary production and export efficiency.

Figure 1: Map showing the underway sampling locations along the SAMBA Monitoring Line between Cape Town (CT) and Tristan da Cunha Island (TA). Sampling was conducted hourly during Leg 1, every 2 hours during Leg 2, and every 4 hours during Leg 3.

Data presented here were collected along the South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation Basin-wide Array (SAMBA) Monitoring Line during the 2025 Gough Island Relief voyage (Fig. 1). Seawater samples were collected from the ship's underway system (at ca. 7 m depth) into 50 mL centrifuge tubes that were rinsed three times prior to collection and stored immediately at -80°C . Samples were analysed ashore using a SEAL analytical AA500 AutoAnalyser.

Surface nutrient concentrations were consistently low along much of the SAMBA Monitoring Line, reflecting the oligotrophic character of the South Atlantic surface ocean (Fig. 2). Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) remained uniformly low relative to silicate east of the prime meridian, whereas higher concentrations were observed further west. PO_4^{3-} concentrations were comparatively stable throughout the transect, while SiO_4^{4-} displayed moderate spatial variability. N:P ratios remained well below Redfield proportions across most of the transect, confirming widespread nitrogen limitation in surface waters (Fig. 3A). The divergence among nutrient concentrations indicates strong biological control of surface DIN. Elevated Si:N ratios (Fig. 3B) at stations with low DIN indicated that silicate was not limiting relative to nitrogen and remained largely unused once nitrogen was depleted. Similarly, Si:P ratios that approached or exceeded Redfield-like values (Fig. 3C) reflected the persistence of silicate relative to phosphate under oligotrophic conditions. Collectively, these low nutrient concentrations and stoichiometric patterns are consistent with a surface system dominated by regenerated production, favouring

Figure 2: Longitudinal distribution of surface (ca. 7 m) dissolved inorganic nutrient concentrations along the SAMBA Monitoring Line. Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN = $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$; blue line), phosphate (PO_4^{3-} ; orange line), and silicate (SiO_4^{4-} ; green line).

Figure 3: Longitudinal variability of surface (ca. 7 m) nutrient stoichiometry along the SAMBA Monitoring Line showing (A) N:P (DIN: PO_4^{3-}), (B) Si:N (SiO_4^{4-} :DIN), and (C) Si:P (SiO_4^{4-} : PO_4^{3-}) ratios. Dashed horizontal lines indicate reference stoichiometries: Redfield N:P = 16:1, Si:N = 1, and Si:P = 16.

small phytoplankton and permitting episodic diatom growth only when nitrogen is temporarily replenished.

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19. THE EFFECTS OF AQUACULTURE EFFLUENT ON ROCKY SHORE ORGANISMS IN MARSHSTRAND, EAST LONDON

Rocky shores are biodiversity hotspots that support a wide range of benthic organisms, play a crucial role in marine food webs, and contribute significantly to coastal livelihoods. However, rocky shore ecosystems face increasing pressure from human activities such as harvesting and coastal development. The rapid expansion of aquaculture activities along the South African coast has also raised concerns about the potential effects of effluent on nearby marine communities. In the Eastern Cape, the expanding practice of abalone farming generates effluent containing organic matter, such as uneaten feed and faeces, which can lead to nutrient enrichment and potentially alter the composition of nearby rocky shore communities.

This study investigates the effects of aquaculture effluent on rocky shore organisms by comparing a site near Marshstrand in the Eastern Cape, exposed to effluent from an abalone farm, with a control site at Haga-Haga, located some distance from the discharge point. Measurements at each site were recorded in 2022 and again in 2024, along three transect lines from the high to the low shore. Along each transect, 50×50 cm quadrats were used to record the density of each species. Where possible, 90 individuals per species were measured to compare mean body size between sites. Patellid limpets (*Cymbula oculus* and *Scutellastra granularis*) were chosen as bioindicator species because of their sensitivity to pollution and their well-understood biology. Both are semi-motile and cannot migrate easily from a pollution source.

Figure 2. Mean densities (ind.0.25 m²) of (A) *C. oculus* and (B) *S. granularis* at control and effluent sites in 2022 and 2024. Sites sharing the same letter (a, b, or c) are not significantly different from each other, while those with different letters are.

The density of *C. oculus* increased at both sites over the study period and was significantly higher at the effluent discharge site. In contrast, the density of *S. granularis* was significantly lower at the effluent discharge site compared to the control site, and continued to decrease over the study period (Fig. 1). Shell length was found to

Figure 1. Mean shell size (mm) of (A) *C. oculus* and (B) *S. granularis* (B) at control and effluent sites in 2022 and 2024. Sites sharing the same letter (a, b, or c) are not significantly different from each other, while those with different letters are.

be a poor metric for detecting direct effects of effluent discharge, providing weaker signals than density. For *C. oculus*, shell length did not differ between sites or years, with large individuals (more than 40 mm) present at both sites. The shell length of *S. granularis* was smaller at the effluent discharge site than at the control site in 2022, but this pattern was reversed in 2024 (Fig. 2). Nutrient enrichment from effluent discharge is known to increase macroalgal production and, in turn, food availability, which may lead to increased growth/survival, potentially enhancing reproductive output and leading to higher limpet abundances. This could explain the high numbers of *C. oculus* at the effluent discharge site in both years. However, this species is frequently harvested (unlike *S. granularis*), which may explain the low density at the control site (Fig. 1), although there was no evidence of harvesting at either site (no discarded shucked shells or harvesters present). Ongoing monitoring and water quality assessments may shed light on other factors that may influence the patterns observed in this study.

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20. EFFECTS OF EXPERIMENTAL MANIPULATIONS OF THE DENSITY OF CYMBULA GRANATINA ON MACRO ALGAL COVER

Due to their accessibility, intertidal rocky shores are prone to high harvesting pressures. Most harvesting on the South African west coast is directed at patellid limpets such as *Cymbula granatina*. These limpets play a central role in structuring rocky shore community composition, and their depletion may alter ecosystems through direct or indirect effects on other species. This study was conducted to evaluate the impacts of different harvesting levels of *C. granatina* on rocky shore community structure, in particular macroalgal cover.

Densities of *C. granatina* were manipulated at two intertidal sites within a no-take zone of the Table Mountain National Park Marine Protected Area on the west coast of the Cape Peninsula, South Africa. The study took place from November 2017 to June 2020. There were four exclusion cage treatment levels ranging from maximum natural densities to entirely depleted, categorised as follows: 100% of natural densities (>12 individuals/plot, where no reduction of density was undertaken—this was the control); 50% (7–9 individuals/plot, lightly harvested); 10% (single limpet/plot, heavily harvested); 0% (no limpets/plot, depleted).

At the start of the experiment, community composition did not differ among the four density treatments at either site (Fig. 1). Differences began to emerge after four months at Scarborough South and after five months at Scarborough North. These changes were associated with increases in macroalgal percentage cover and were evident only during periods of high algal abundance outside of winter months. Macroalgal cover increased in the low-density (0 and 10%) treatment plots, which showed higher cover than the higher-density plots. This increase did not occur in the natural-density (50 and 100%) control plots, where limpet populations were not reduced (Fig. 2).

As hypothesised, limpet removal or substantial reduction of density altered community composition, although responses varied between sites and over time, reflecting natural seasonal changes in macroalgal cover. The absence of any limpet-density effect in times when the algae were scarce implies that influences other than grazing were controlling their abundance. This could be related to a reduction in nutrients and light when upwelling diminishes in the cooler months of the year, as upwelling-favourable winds decline. Macroalgae flourished in exclusion cages with few or no limpets, as reduced grazing pressure and competition for space promoted algal recruitment on rock surfaces previously occupied by limpets. Overall, our findings support the need for ecosystem-based marine management, because of the strong influences exerted by limpets on associated communities. Harvesting should not reduce *C. granatina* densities below 50% of natural pristine levels – below this level, algal cover increases to dominate community composition.

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Figure 1. Mean percentage cover of macroalgae in relation to limpet density levels over time, at (A) Scarborough North and (B) Scarborough South. Asterisks indicate time points at which limpet densities had significant effects ($P < 0.05$) on macroalgal cover among treatment levels. The dotted line indicates a break in sampling before plots were revisited in February 2020.

Figure 2. Mean (+1 SE) percentage cover of algae found in the plots at (A) Scarborough North and (B) Scarborough South. Different letters above bars indicate significant differences (post-hoc tests, $P < 0.05$) in limpet density between plots.

21. INFLUENCE OF FLOW VARIABILITY ON BENTHIC MACROFAUNAL COMMUNITIES IN FLUVIALLY DOMINATED ESTUARIES

Estuarine benthic macrofauna (e.g. polychaetes, molluscs, and crustaceans) form an important component of aquatic food webs, acting both as primary consumers and as an important food source for higher trophic levels. They also contribute to nutrient, carbon and detritus cycling. These organisms are widely used as indicators of ecosystem health because they are easy and cost-effective to sample. They also occupy a wide range of habitats and are therefore continuously exposed to local environmental conditions. Benthic macrofauna have been shown to be useful for assessing the effects of altered river flow on estuarine ecosystems, a major threat to estuaries in South Africa. Stable, low-flow conditions support higher species abundance, while high flows can displace or reduce benthic populations. Extreme events such as floods or droughts can intensify these impacts, potentially eliminating local populations and altering community structure. This study investigated how flow variability influences benthic macrofaunal communities at two fluvially (riverine) dominated estuaries in South Africa, the Orange River and Kei River estuaries (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. A map of South Africa showing the locations of the Orange River Estuary (square) and the Kei River Estuary (star).

Benthic invertebrates were sampled biannually at each estuary during 2017–2018, using a Van Veen grab (a clamshell-style sampler for collecting sediment from the bottom of aquatic systems), during high and low-flow periods. Five replicate samples were collected at each of 18 stations in the Orange River Estuary and 11 stations in the Kei River Estuary. Overall, the benthic macrofaunal community was dominated by polychaetes (*Capitella capitata*, *Ceratonereis keiskamma*, *Prionospio sexoculata* and *Desdemona ornata*), with contributions from crustaceans (*Grandidierella lutosa*) and insect larvae (Fig. 2). In the Orange River Estuary species composition was similar between the two flow periods, with *D. ornata* contributing 45–50% of total benthic density. In the Kei River Estuary, species composition was also similar between flow periods, but densities differed considerably. For example, the amphipod *G. lutosa* contributed 74.7% and 21.5% during low and high flow periods, respectively (Fig. 2). *D. ornata* was only present during low flow periods. Species diversity did not differ significantly across flow periods in either estuary, but species richness was higher in the Kei River Estuary during low flow (Fig. 3).

The results show that river flow influences benthic macrofaunal communities, though its effects are site-specific. Species diversity did not differ significantly between flow periods in either estuary, and species richness in the Orange River Estuary did not increase under low-flow conditions, as anticipated. The observed patterns may reflect long-term reductions in freshwater

Figure 2. Percentage composition of benthic macrofaunal density in the Orange River Estuary during high (OHF) and low (OLF) flow periods, and in the Kei River Estuary during high (KHF) and low (KLF) flow periods.

inflow due to municipal, industrial, and agricultural activities, which have already shaped community structure. The need for site-specific monitoring and management to improve flow regimes is emphasised.

Figure 3. Mean (black diamond) and median (solid horizontal line) values for (a) species diversity and (b) species richness during high-flow and low-flow periods in the Kei and Orange River estuaries. Asterisks indicate where there was a significant difference between flow periods.

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22. THE ROLE OF RIVER FLOW IN SHAPING NURSERY VALUE FOR LARVAL FISHES IN A TEMPERATE ESTUARY

Freshwater inflow is a key variable shaping estuarine ecosystem processes, and changes in the magnitude or timing of flow can have profound impacts on resident and dependent faunal species. Along the east coast of South Africa, projected increases in precipitation due to climate change may lead to increased river flow and sediment input. This has potential implications for larval fish survival and the long-term sustainability of estuarine-dependent coastal fisheries. However, the effects of altered river flow on larval fish dynamics remain poorly understood. This study addressed this gap, with a focus on the Kei River Estuary in the Eastern Cape (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The geographic location of the Kei River Estuary, showing the positions of the sampling sites.

Larval fish were sampled seasonally at eight sites in the Kei River Estuary between September 2016 and June 2018 to capture variability associated with different river flow regimes (Fig. 1). At each site, two sub-surface replicates were collected using modified WP2 plankton nets fitted with flow meters (Fig. 2a, b). Samples were subsequently analysed in the laboratory, where larval fishes were identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level under a microscope. Densities were calculated per volume of water filtered (Fig 2c).

Figure 2. (a, b) Sampling and (c) laboratory analysis of larval fishes.

The highest densities of larval fishes were recorded during intermediate flow conditions, ranging from 0–17,985 larvae per 100 m³ (Fig 3a). These flow conditions were also associated with the greatest species richness ($S = 11$) and diversity ($H' = 1.7$), whereas the lowest values were observed under high-flow conditions ($S = 0–2$; $H' = 0–0.3$) (Fig 3b, c). These patterns are consistent with the Intermediate

Figure 3. Mean (black diamond), median (solid black lines) and range of (a) larval fish density (b) species richness, and (c) Shannon-Weiner diversity index, recorded in the Kei River Estuary during the sampling period (Sep 2016 – June 2018).

Disturbance Hypothesis, which predicts that species diversity is maximised at intermediate levels of disturbance. At these levels, competitive exclusion by dominant species is reduced, while conditions remain sufficiently stable to allow species establishment, unlike under high disturbance regimes. The results of this study demonstrate that river flow is a key driver of larval fish assemblages and underscore the importance of maintaining natural flow regimes. This is critical for species that rely on estuaries as nursery areas, as larval survival ultimately determines recruitment to adult populations.

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23. INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF DIEL VERTICAL MIGRATION IN LARVAL CONNECTIVITY MODELLING

This study evaluates how diel vertical migration (DVM) influences the dispersal patterns of particles simulating larval anchovy and sardine along the South African continental shelf. Understanding these behavioural mechanisms is fundamental to managing these ecologically and economically vital species. The primary objectives were to determine whether DVM (1) enhances larval retention within productive shelf waters and (2) increases connectivity among Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), compared to a purely passive dispersal strategy.

We coupled the 3-km-resolution Coastal and Regional Ocean Community (CROCO) hydrodynamic model with the Ichthyop Lagrangian particle-tracking tool (<https://ichthyop.org>) to simulate the 3D marine environment off South Africa. To ensure statistical power, 100,000 particles were released across major coastal spawning grounds and tracked over 30-day periods. We applied Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) to map the probability distribution of larval locations after 30 days. To evaluate behavioural differences, we calculated spatial density differences between the DVM and non-DVM simulations. Transport distances were summarised using boxplots, while connectivity and retention were measured by analysing particle overlap with MPAs (Fig. 1).

The findings revealed a stark contrast in the fate of particles driven by larval swimming behaviour. Passive particles released at the sea surface were particularly susceptible to being entrained by the Agulhas Current and prevailing wind-driven transport. In contrast, the simulated DVM strategy promoted the retention of particles within the 200 m isobath, effectively mitigating offshore export (Fig. 1a). The integration of DVM behaviour also promoted the formation of high-density patches of larvae in key regions, which is a key factor for successful recruitment. On average, particles with DVM behaviour tended to travel longer distances (Fig. 1b), which is critical for metapopulation resilience.

Regional analysis further highlighted the strategic advantage of simulated DVM across different coastal systems. Higher density patches of larvae were found in the western region of the Agulhas Bank, which would promote the recruitment of larvae to the productive region of the southern Benguela (Fig. 1a). In the KwaZulu-Natal Bight, more particles were found in the Coastal Counter Current during DVM simulations. On the west coast, fewer particles were swept away by the Benguela Jet, suggesting that the ability to avoid surface winds and strong surface currents is key to successful recruitment in this region.

In conclusion, DVM is a primary driver of connectivity between MPAs and the broader coastal ecosystem, significantly increasing the likelihood that larvae remain within the shelf system rather than being lost offshore. The simulations demonstrated that passive dispersal results in a fragmented population with limited exchange between regions. Conversely, the increased retention provided by DVM allows for more frequent transport of particles between existing protected areas. These findings suggest that the current MPA network may be more biologically linked than passive models indicate. Accounting for behavioural traits such as DVM is essential for designing effective conservation strategies that reflect real-world larval transport.

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Figure 1. Larval dispersal at 10–15 m: (a) spatial density difference between DVM and non-DVM behaviours, and (b) distribution of cumulative dispersal distances. AB = Agulhas Bank, KZNB = KwaZulu-Natal Bight.

24. SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN THE AGULHAS CURRENT DENSITY STRUCTURE

The Agulhas Current is a strong Western Boundary Current, that flows along the east coast of South Africa (Fig. 1). It plays a vital role in global ocean circulation and environmental equilibrium of the global climate system by transporting heat and salt polewards. Variations in time and space of the core of the Agulhas Current affect temperature, salinity, sea level distribution, and the overall movement of water masses. Thus, understanding the variations in the density structure of the Agulhas Current at seasonal and long-term scales is essential to derive critical indicators of climate variability, monitor long-term trends, and infer possible impacts, including changes in rainfall patterns, ecosystem dynamics and marine productivity.

Figure 1. Surface map showing the mean (1993–2021) climatology of the speed of the Agulhas Current (colour shading) and stream lines with arrows showing current direction, derived from the CNES-CLS 2022 mean dynamic topography of the ocean. Agulhas System Climate Array (ASCA) transect stations are shown as magenta triangles. Thin contours represent isobaths.

This study characterises the seasonal changes in the density structure of the Agulhas Current using long-term observations and infers the dynamics driving these variations. Seawater density was computed from *in situ* profiles of temperature and salinity (1991–2020) from the World Ocean Atlas 2023 database, which has a spatial resolution of 25 km. Figure 2 shows the vertical distribution of the austral seasonal seawater density anomalies along the Agulhas System Climate Array (ASCA) transect. Seasonal means were computed as December–February (summer), March–May (autumn), June–August (winter), and September–November (spring). Seasonal anomalies were estimated by subtracting the seasonal means from the overall mean climatology (1991–2020).

Figure 2. Vertical distribution of the seasonal climatology (1991–2020) of density anomalies in the upper 500 m along the ASCA transect. Panels show the summer (A), autumn (B), winter (C), and spring (D) seasons. White shading below 100 m depth is the continental shelf.

Distinct patterns of fluctuating positive and negative density anomalies were observed along the ASCA transect (Fig. 2). Negative anomalies indicate local water conditions that are lighter than the surrounding waters. Conversely, positive anomalies indicate the opposite. Closely spaced contours indicate stronger density gradients, while loosely spaced contours reflect weaker gradients. The strongest negative density anomalies and gradients were observed in summer (Fig. 2A). These strong gradients occupied a thin layer of the upper ocean, extending roughly across the transect. This layer was shallower near the coast than offshore (Fig. 2A). During autumn (Fig. 2B), negative anomalies and density gradients were weaker. Negative density anomalies in the upper ocean are generally associated with strong stratification, intense solar heating, and weaker winds, leading to buoyancy driven circulation, as seen by the roughly horizontal contours in summer (Fig. 2A), and upward tilting of density contours toward the coast (Fig. 2B). The pattern observed in summer, and autumn was reversed in winter (Fig. 2C) and spring (Fig. 2D), with positive density anomalies in the upper ocean.

This study shows that the upper ocean density structure of the Agulhas Current exhibits a notable seasonality that is dynamically modulated by the tilting and flattening of the isopycnals. This behaviour can be used as an indicator of environmental change. Regular observations are required to monitor this behaviour.

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25. DRIVERS OF AGULHAS CURRENT CIRCULATION AND VARIABILITY IN A REGIONAL OCEAN MODEL

The Agulhas Current (AC) flows south-westward along the east coast of South Africa (Fig. 1). Variability in the AC strongly influences regional weather and climate across southern Africa and affects the composition and distribution of marine biota. This variability exhibits two distinct modes: the northern part of the current is relatively stable, whereas the southern part is considerably more unstable (Fig. 1). Flow stability is intrinsically related to vorticity (the tendency of a fluid parcel to rotate), with highly unstable flow generally associated with elevated vorticity values.

Figure 1. Sea surface temperature around South Africa on 9 February 2024 from the Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis (OSTIA) system. Contours represent isobaths.

The present study aims to identify the controls on circulation and variability in the Agulhas system. To achieve this, we used output from a 3 km-resolution hydrodynamic model and applied a mathematical framework known as the mean barotropic vorticity balance (VB). The VB framework enables the sources and sinks of vorticity to be identified and typically comprises six terms, each representing a different physical process. Overall vorticity balance ($VB=0$) is achieved by summing all six terms. For simplicity, only four terms are presented here, based on their importance in achieving $VB=0$. The relative importance of the terms was determined by evaluating their individual and combined contributions to conserving VB. Figure 2 presents the most important terms contributing to $VB=0$. Positive (negative) values of the advection of planetary vorticity (APV, Fig. 2A) indicate poleward (equatorward) flow. Its southward strengthening reflects the increase in planetary vorticity with latitude. The prevalence of a continuous band of positive APV along the coast, particularly north of 34°S, indicates that

the current is largely stable and primarily maintained by the meridional gradient in the Earth's vorticity. The vorticity associated with bottom pressure, known as bottom pressure torque (BPT, Fig. 2B), arises from the interaction between the flow and seafloor topography. It results from variations in bottom pressure along sloping isobaths. Positive (negative) BPT values are associated with equatorward (poleward) deflections of the depth-integrated flow and the generation of vorticity. At scales of approximately 100 km and smaller, highly turbulent flows emerge as a result of nonlinear processes. The advection of vorticity by these nonlinear processes (NLA) is shown in Figure 2C. NLA closely resembles BPT (Fig. 2B) in its spatial distribution and magnitude, but with opposite signs, indicating a near-balance between the two terms. This suggests that NLA drives the flow across isobaths, whereas BPT acts to constrain the flow along isobaths. The sum of BPT and NLA is shown in Figure 2D. Together, these terms largely offset APV (Fig. 2A), particularly along the western boundary. Exceptions occur at localised regions where the shelf-break changes orientation near 34° and 36°S, corresponding to the northern and southern slopes of the Agulhas Bank, where AC meanders are commonly observed (Fig. 1).

These results indicate that different processes govern the circulation and variability of the AC. The balance between APV and BPT+NLA dominates over most of the region, except near 34° and 36°S. This suggests that other mechanisms, such as bottom drag and wind stress curl, become locally important. Interactions between the background flow, friction, eddies, and sloping topography may therefore generate variability with distinct biogeochemical and ecosystem responses north and south of 34°S.

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Figure 2. Terms of the barotropic vorticity balance framework showing (A) advection of planetary vorticity (APV), and (B) vorticity of the bottom pressure (BPT), and (C) nonlinear advection of vorticity (NLA), with (D) showing the sum of (B) and (C). Contours indicate isobaths.

26. THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS AS A FORERUNNER IN GLOBAL ISLAND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH

Island ecosystems, particularly those in the sub-Antarctic region of the Southern Ocean, provide unique natural ‘laboratories’ to explore how climate variations, biological invasions, and other anthropogenic drivers of change impact ecosystem functioning. South Africa has jurisdiction over two sub-Antarctic Islands, namely Marion and Prince Edward, which collectively comprise the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) archipelago (Fig. 1). These islands seasonally host globally significant populations of breeding marine mammals (elephant seals, fur seals, and various cetaceans) and seabirds (including penguins, albatrosses and petrels, among others). Scientists have long been interested in understanding how this island ecosystem is able to sustain such large populations of top predators, given that chlorophyll *a* concentration (an indicator of primary productivity) in the Southern Ocean is generally low, despite high nutrient availability.

Previous research has indicated that waters in the immediate vicinity of the PEIs are a hotspot of primary production. This enhanced production is commonly referred to as the island mass effect, which results from the complex interplay between various factors. This includes interactions between the surrounding circulation and the underlying bathymetry, localised upwelling, and nutrient runoff from the islands. Top predators are thought to contribute substantially to nutrient enrichment in the vicinity of the islands because they produce large quantities of organic waste which, when washed off the island, fertilises the surrounding waters.

We conducted an extensive review of all globally available, published research articles that have investigated the island mass effect. Between 1956, when the island mass effect was first recognised, and September 2025, a total of 120 articles about this ecological process across 60 unique and fragile island ecoregions (Fig. 1) have been published. Notably, the island mass effect that periodically occurs at the PEIs is the most studied across the global ocean, with 11 published research articles having specifically documented its occurrence and impacts on the marine environment (Fig. 1). This highlights the pivotal role

played by South Africa’s research community in general, and the PEIs in particular, in enhancing the global understanding of the island mass effect for maintaining structure and functioning within island ecosystems. In this regard, the DFFE and the South African National Research Foundation provide the critical leadership and funding to drive South African research and long-term ecosystem monitoring conducted across the Southern Ocean.

Despite the notable body of research on the island mass effect at the PEIs, we still do not fully understand all the mechanisms underpinning the enhancement of primary production. However, the foundation laid by this research arguably makes the PEIs the most suitable location to improve global understanding of the island mass effect. Recent investigations have highlighted a changing oceanographic environment at the PEIs. Addressing how these changes may affect the islands’ top predator populations and further understanding the role of these top predators in sustaining the island mass effect, will provide critical insights into the potential future responses of sub-Antarctic Island ecosystems to global warming and variability.

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Figure 3. Global map of island ecoregions where scientific research articles on the island mass effect have been published between 1956 and September 2025. The colour of each island indicates the number of articles published. Only islands with more than three published articles have been included in this figure.

27. DISTRIBUTIONS OF CARBONATE SYSTEM PARAMETERS AROUND THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS IN 2025

The Southern Ocean (SO) accounts for more than 40% of the cumulative global oceanic anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) absorption, making it a key region for CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere. However, the SO is vulnerable to ocean acidification as atmospheric CO₂ levels continue to rise. Thus, understanding the distributions of CO₂ partial pressure (pCO₂) and pH in this region is important. Here, we present the spatial distributions of the sea surface temperature (SST), salinity (SSS), pCO₂, and pH between South Africa and the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) (Fig. 1) and around the PEIs (Fig. 2), sampled during the 2025 Marion Island Relief voyage from 22 April to 15 May 2025.

Figure 1. Surface ocean distributions of temperature (A), salinity (B), pCO₂ (C), and pH (D) between South Africa and the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs). Green boxes indicate the area around the PEIs.

The pCO₂ in the sea surface layer and in the atmosphere was measured underway using a non-dispersive infrared spectrometer (Li-Cor®7000 CO₂/H₂O Analyzer) integrated into a General Oceanics (model 8050) underway pCO₂ system. The surface pH was measured underway using a Sea-Bird Scientific SeaFET Ocean pH sensor. South of 45°S, SST was below 12°C, while SSS was <34 PSU (Fig. 1).

While the area north of 45°S acted as a sink, the colder, less saline, and lower pH (<8) surface waters south of 45°S had high pCO₂ (Fig. 1), which exceeded the measured average atmospheric CO₂ of 435 μatm. At the PEIs, the pCO₂ values (Fig. 2B) in surface seawater ranged from 364 to 475 μatm, while the pH varied from 7.62 to 8.02. The highest pCO₂ values, associated with low pH (Fig. 2C), were observed on the western side of Prince Edward Island and in the channel between the two islands. Surface pCO₂ on the PEI shelf mostly exceeded the atmospheric CO₂ level of 435 μatm by

Figure 2. Surface ocean distributions of temperature (A), pCO₂ (B), and pH (C) around PEIs within the green box shown in Figure 1. Red boxes highlight pCO₂ values below 435 μatm.

Figure 3. Time series of surface ocean pCO₂ (A) and pH (B) around PEIs within the boundaries: (37.25–38.1°S; 46.4–47.24°E) as indicated by the green box in Figure 2. Red boxes highlight pCO₂ values below atmospheric (ATM_pCO₂) values.

about 30 μatm (Fig. 3A), indicating that the area acted as a source of CO₂ to the atmosphere. Three periods of low pCO₂ <435 μatm were observed in the open ocean around the PEIs (Figs. 2 and 3: red boxes), indicating open ocean dynamics (e.g. lower SST, among others) that reduce surface pCO₂ values. Generally high pCO₂ (>435 μatm) (Fig. 3A) and low pH below 8 (Fig. 3B) are indicative of ocean acidification. The continuation of ocean acidification in the marine environment on the PEI shelf may reduce the availability of carbonate ions needed by organisms such as corals, shellfish, and plankton that build their skeletal structures from calcium carbonate. Thus, as pH continues to decrease, these organisms face reduced growth rates and increased mortality. It is thus critical to monitor pCO₂ and pH in the PEI region.

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28. INTERANNUAL DIFFERENCES IN ZOOPLANKTON COMMUNITY STRUCTURE AT THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS

Zooplankton play a central role in pelagic ecosystems by mediating the transfer of energy from phytoplankton to the top predators. Consequently, changes in their community structure can influence ecosystem functioning and food-web dynamics. Monitoring temporal variability in taxonomic composition, abundance and size structure is therefore essential for understanding ecosystem change. This report examines interannual variability in the zooplankton community at the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) between 2016 and 2019 (Fig. 1, Table 1).

Data were collected during annual relief voyages along two routinely sampled transects (see Report Card 30). Zooplankton were sampled using 200 μm mesh MultiNets and Bongo nets. Samples were imaged using a ZooScan system, processed with imaging software, and taxonomically classified in Ecotaxa with manual validation to estimate abundance and biovolume. In 2016 and 2017, both net types were deployed to a maximum depth of 500 m, whereas in 2018 and 2019, Bongo nets were deployed to 200 m. To ensure interannual comparability, subsequent analyses were restricted to samples from the upper 200 m.

Copepoda dominated the zooplankton community throughout the study period, comprising 85–95% of total abundance and 31–35% of total biovolume, underscoring their central role in the pelagic food web at the PEIs (Fig. 1). Within the copepod assemblage, Calanoida and Cyclopoida contributed similarly to abundance, but Calanoida accounted for most of copepod biovolume (83–94%), reflecting their larger body size. Cyclopoida were primarily represented by small-bodied *Oithona* species occupying lower trophic positions. Ostracoda (2–5%) and Chaetognatha (1–4%) were the next most abundant taxa. Despite their relatively low abundances, Chaetognatha contributed substantially to total biovolume (31–45%) owing to their larger size as predators. In contrast, the smaller-sized Ostracoda contributed minimally (<2% total biovolume), despite comparable abundances.

Cluster analysis of log-transformed abundances revealed clear interannual variations. The high-abundance years, 2018 and 2019 (~ 520 – 557 ind m^{-3} ; Table 1), showed greater similarity (70%) and comparable community compositions (Fig. 1). In contrast, 2016 and 2017 exhibited overall lower mean abundances (~ 76 – 99 ind m^{-3} ; Table 1) and formed separate clusters, with 2017 separating from 2016 at 70% similarity. This distinction was associated with higher relative contributions of Chaetognatha, Mollusca, and Cnidaria in 2017, and elevated abundances of Chromista in 2016 (Fig. 1). Together, Copepoda, Ostracoda, and Chaetognatha consistently dominated the community, accounting for 94–99% of total abundance and 64–81% of biovolume, with relatively stable proportions across years. This suggests that interannual variability was driven primarily by fluctuations in the overall abundance of these dominant groups, rather than by substantial shifts in community structure. In contrast to abundance, biovolume showed

greater intra-annual variability, reflecting its sensitivity to large-bodied, low-abundance taxa. Episodic increases in Euphausiacea and Cnidaria contributed disproportionately to overall biomass, resulting in marked fluctuations.

Figure 4. Pie charts illustrating the relative contribution of all taxonomic groups (top row), and all taxonomic groups excluding Copepoda (bottom row), to total zooplankton abundance within the upper 200 m of the water column.

Table 1. Mean abundance and biovolume of zooplankton during 2016–2019 over (0–500 m) and (0–200 m) depth ranges. Grey shading indicates data over 0–500 m.

Year	Depth range (m)	Mean Abundance (ind m^{-3})	Mean Biomass ($\text{mm}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$)
2016	0–500	70.65	41.04
2017	0–500	52.53	33.16
2016	0–200	75.75	18.33
2017	0–200	98.95	47.33
2018	0–200	519.83	192.68
2019	0–200	557.35	85.50

Our findings indicate that although the zooplankton community at the PEIs maintained a relatively stable core composition, total abundance exhibited substantial interannual variability. In contrast, variability in biovolume was driven by modest increases in large, numerically scarce taxa and associated shifts in size structure. While overall abundance and composition were similar in 2018 and 2019, biovolume in 2018 was approximately twice as high (Table 1), reflecting a greater contribution of larger organisms. This underscores the importance of size structure, rather than abundance and composition alone, as a key driver of biomass variability. These interannual changes were closely linked to physical oceanographic conditions and may have important implications for food-web efficiency and the capacity of higher trophic levels to meet their energetic demands.

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29. ENVIRONMENTAL INFLUENCE ON ZOOPLANKTON COMMUNITY STRUCTURE AT THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS

Zooplankton form the base of the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) ecosystem, transferring energy from phytoplankton to larger predators. Mesoscale hydrographic features, particularly fronts and eddies, are thought to play a central role in structuring plankton communities. We examined environmental influences on zooplankton collected over four consecutive years at the PEIs during annual relief voyages to Marion Island.

Zooplankton were collected using 200 μm -meshed MultiNets and Bongo nets in the upper 500 m (2016–2017) or 200 m (2018–2019), together with CTD deployments measuring temperature, salinity, and chlorophyll *a* (*chl**a*). Samples were analysed using a ZooScan and classified via Ecotaxa. Positions of the northern, middle and southern branches of the sub-Antarctic Front (N-, M-, S-SAF) and Antarctic Polar Front (APF) were identified using Absolute Dynamic Topography, and satellite-derived sea surface temperatures. Relationships between zooplankton metrics and environmental variables were investigated.

In 2016 and 2017, the S-SAF was positioned close to the PEIs. Its proximity likely enhanced current velocities over the inter-island shelf, limiting retention and inhibiting Taylor column formation. The *chl**a* concentrations (a proxy measure of phytoplankton biomass) were moderate, and zooplankton abundance and biovolume in the upper 500 m were comparable (Fig. 1). During 2018, the S-SAF was located to the south of the islands, with reduced current velocities around the islands. This promoted a retentive and productive regime, resulting in the highest *chl**a* recorded across the study period. In 2019, although the S-SAF remained close to the islands, a pronounced meander developed over the region. This likely enhanced retention, with mean zooplankton abundance in the upper 200 m (520 ind m^{-3}) similar to that in 2018

(577 ind m^{-3}). This suggests that both frontal position and orientation influence biological accumulation. While the mean zooplankton abundance in 2018 was similar to that in 2019, the mean biovolume ($193 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$) was approximately double (Fig. 1), suggesting the presence of larger individuals in 2018. Zooplankton biovolume showed a strong, positive correlation (Spearman's rank test) with *chl**a* in 2017 and 2018, indicating a trophic response to enhanced food availability. Increased primary production likely supported greater somatic growth or favoured larger taxa. In 2018, a cold-core cyclonic eddy of Antarctic origin transported productive waters into the region, further enhancing the observed zooplankton biomass.

The 2016–2017 abundances and biovolumes shown here are not directly comparable to those in 2018–2019 due to the difference in sampling depths (see Report 34 for comparable values). Nevertheless, the position and orientation of the S-SAF played a strong role in governing the zooplankton abundance, biovolume, and community composition at the PEIs by modulating water mass distributions, retention, and local productivity. It is crucial to continue the monitoring of variations in frontal positions to understand spatial and temporal changes in the zooplankton community at the PEIs.

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Figure 1. Abundance (ind m^{-3} , top row) and biovolume ($\text{mm}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, bottom row) of zooplankton at each station sampled in the upper 500 m (2016–2017), and 200 m (2018–2019) overlaid on Absolute Dynamic Topography (ADT), highlighting the positions of the middle (dot-dash line) and southern (solid line) branches of the sub-Antarctic Front (red) and the northern (dashed line) and middle (dot-dash line) of the Antarctic Polar Front (black). Current velocity is represented by arrows.

30. THE INFLUENCE OF SAMPLING APPROACH ON ZOOPLANKTON MONITORING

Annual monitoring of the zooplankton community at the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs, Fig. 1) has been ongoing since 2013. However, changes in sampling methodology over time may have influenced the nature of zooplankton capture, with implications for the interpretation of temporal and spatial variability. This study examined samples collected between 2016 and 2019 to evaluate how variations in sampling design may have affected the observed patterns in zooplankton community structure.

Figure 5. Bathymetry map showing the geographical positions of stations sampled in the upstream (red box) and inter-island (blue box) regions, and additional stations sampled in 2018. Contours show the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans.

Zooplankton were collected using MultiNets and Bongo nets to a maximum depth of 500 m in 2016 and 2017, while Bongo nets were sampled to 200 m in 2018 and 2019. Each year, a north–south upstream transect and an east–west inter-island transect were sampled, with additional downstream stations sampled in 2018 (Fig. 1). Samples were analysed using ZooScan imaging software and taxonomically classified via EcoTaxa with manual validation to obtain abundance and biovolume estimates. This was the first study in the region to employ imaging technology for zooplankton analysis. The approach enabled rapid processing of sample aliquots and produced digital archives that can be re-examined.

Abundance (which highlights the more numerous, small organisms) and biovolume (which highlights the contribution of larger organisms) characterise different aspects of the same community. By providing measurements of organism dimensions, imaging analysis facilitates the estimation of biovolume and size-structure comparisons. This enables a more rounded assessment of the effects of sampling approach on observed patterns in zooplankton communities than can be obtained from abundance alone. Wilcoxon rank-sum tests were used to compare zooplankton abundances and biovolumes across categorical variables such as time of day (day vs night) and net type.

The abundance and biovolume of zooplankton each differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) across different net types and years, with generally higher values from Bongo nets. However, as net use was confounded with sampling year (MultiNets in 2016–2017; Bongos in 2018–2019), interannual and gear effects could not be

Figure 2. Mean abundance and biovolume of zooplankton in the upper 200 m and 500 m during 2016 and 2017.

disentangled. During cruises when both nets were deployed (e.g., 2016), net type remained confounded with spatial variation due to the sampling design. Variations in sampling depth further complicated interpretation. Mean abundances integrated over only the upper 200 m were higher than when integrated over the full 500 m. This is the result of aggregation of zooplankton near the surface due to diel vertical migration (DVM; Fig. 2). However, in 2016, the biovolume was lower when integrated over the upper 200 m, as larger but less numerous organisms were found at greater depths. Therefore, sampling to 200 m may provide a higher count per volume but may exclude deeper-occurring large organisms (e.g. Chaetognatha, Cnidaria), resulting in an underestimation of their total biovolume. The position of the organisms in the water column impacts zooplankton abundance and biovolume estimates and may vary with time of day due to DVM.

Our results show that sampling approach (including net type, sampling time and depth) complicates the interpretation of interannual and spatial variations in zooplankton biomass and community structure. Similar mesh sizes and mouth areas for MultiNets and Bongo nets suggest that gear alone does not explain the observed variations. However, differences in sampling depth and time can significantly influence zooplankton metrics. This demonstrates the need for a consistent sampling approach for long-term monitoring of zooplankton to allow appropriate interpretation of interannual and spatial patterns and changes. In order to better assess gear effects within the existing time series, we recommend replicating deployments of both net types during at least one cruise.

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31. DNA METABARCODING OF MARINE ZOOPLANKTON AT THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS (2022–2024)

The sub-Antarctic Prince Edward Islands are located directly in the pathway of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, with ocean conditions around the Islands strongly influenced by current variability, shifts in major frontal systems, and mesoscale eddies. The region is a climate change hotspot, affected by a $\sim 1^\circ\text{C}$ increase in sea surface temperature and a southward shift of a major oceanic front over the past few decades. Changes in the functioning of marine pelagic ecosystems can be inferred from the distribution and diversity of zooplankton due to their central role in energy transfer and carbon sequestration. Zooplankton are widely recognised as excellent biological indicators of climate variability and environmental change, because they are short-lived, abundant, diverse, and show rapid responses in community composition.

DNA metabarcoding matches high-throughput sequencing (HTS) data with online DNA barcode reference libraries to rapidly identify multiple species in mixed samples. This tool is well-suited to analyse zooplankton collected with plankton net tows. It complements visual species identification methods, improves biodiversity surveys, and allows for community analysis to track changes in pelagic ecosystems. The geographical isolation of the Prince Edward Islands and dynamic, climate-driven ocean environment surrounding the islands constitute an ideal natural laboratory for investigating pelagic ecosystem responses to climate change. This study is the first to use DNA metabarcoding to analyse zooplankton communities around the islands.

Figure 1. Bathymetry maps of Prince Edward Islands showing stations (black circles) sampled upstream, between, and downstream of the islands (grey), during 2022–2024.

Mesozooplankton sampling was conducted during the annual Marion Island relief voyages from 2022–2024 onboard the SA *Agulhas II*. Each year, samples were collected along transects upstream, downstream, and between the islands (Fig. 1). Zooplankton samples were collected from the upper 200 m of the water column using a 200 μm -mesh Bongo net. DNA was extracted from bulk samples and amplified using multiple taxon-specific mini-barcode primers within the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene region, in combination with a universal mini-barcode primer. The DNA was sequenced using a HTS method at a commercial laboratory to generate unique sequence variants. The sequences were matched to the Barcode of Life Data System and Genbank open-access reference databases to assign sequences to individual species.

Figure 2. Percentage (%) of each taxon group to the total number of species represented in the zooplankton communities sampled during 2022–2024, and the total for all three years combined (All).

In total, 115 zooplankton species were detected across all samples using DNA metabarcoding. Copepoda (36) were the most speciose, followed by Euphausiacea (22), Cnidaria (14), Amphipoda (7), Chaetognatha (7), Ostracoda (7), Mollusca (6), Teleostei (6), Decapoda (5), Annelida (3), Echinodermata (1), and Thecostraca (1) (Fig. 2). Fifty-two species were detected in the 2022 samples, with 64 detected in 2023 and 63 in 2024. Copepods were relatively more diverse in 2022, when sampling focused on open-ocean pelagic waters upstream of the islands. Decapods and euphausiids were more diverse in 2023 and 2024, when the bulk of samples were collected over the inter-island shelf. More detailed comparisons are required to determine if zooplankton communities upstream of the islands are different to those over the inter-island shelf. Zooplankton species indicative of Antarctic waters (e.g. *Calanus simillimus* copepods), sub-Antarctic waters (e.g. *Clausocalanus ingens* copepods), and subtropical waters (e.g. *Thysanopoda obtusifrons* euphausiids) were detected, indicating that the marine environment around the Prince Edward Islands is characterised by the convergence and mixing of water masses of distinct origins. A DNA barcode reference library for the sub-Antarctic region surrounding the islands will improve taxonomic assignments of zooplankton collected in the region, thereby enhancing biodiversity information and ecological monitoring ability.

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32. DNA METABARCODING REVEALS LAND-OCEAN INTERACTIONS AT THE PRINCE EDWARD ISLANDS

Bacterioplankton are a vital, though often overlooked, component of marine ecosystems. They drive essential processes including nutrient cycling, support energy flow and organic matter breakdown, and sustain biogeochemical cycles critical to ocean health and long-term carbon storage. Since bacterioplankton respond rapidly to shifts in nutrient availability, temperature, and other environmental factors, they are effective bioindicators of ecosystem structure, function and health. Importantly, pathogenic (disease-causing) bacterial communities can compromise the health of higher trophic organisms, highlighting their role in shaping overall ecosystem stability.

Figure 1. Map showing the geographic locations of stations sampled upstream, inter-island and downstream at the Prince Edward Islands.

The sub-Antarctic Prince Edward Islands (PEIs) are home to globally significant populations of flying seabirds, penguins and seals. Waste products from these top predators are thought to fertilise the surrounding ocean contributing to the so-called “island mass effect” of increased chlorophyll *a* concentration, and to shifts in bacterioplankton in the immediate vicinity of the islands. This study assessed spatial variations in selected physico-chemical (temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen) and biological (fluorescence) variables at the PEIs between 17 April and 27 May 2025 (Fig. 1). Additionally, deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) metabarcoding of the full-length 16S rRNA gene was used to characterise surface bacterioplankton in the

upstream (west), inter-island and downstream (east) regions of the archipelago. Bacterial community composition displayed no distinct spatial patterns and were dominated by the phyla Proteobacteria, Bacteroidota, Firmicutes, Actinobacteriota and Cyanobacteria (Fig. 2). These phyla play important roles in nutrient cycling, organic matter breakdown and primary production. Correlations with physico-chemical and biological variables were weak and non-significant. The absence of clear spatial patterns and correlations with environmental variables suggests that the island ecosystem was acting as a flow-through system at the time of sampling, with little evidence of water retention.

Importantly, the presence of Firmicutes and Actinobacteriota at station MT03-01 (Fig. 2) point to potential contamination of the marine environment by animal or human activities. This is because these bacteria are known for their antimicrobial activity against fish pathogens, phytopathogens and human pathogens. Further investigations are required to confirm the contamination of the marine environment. These findings highlight the application of DNA metabarcoding to monitor ecosystem functioning and health and support effective management of the PEIs.

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Figure 2. Relative abundance of bacterial phyla at the upstream, inter-island and downstream stations sampled at the Prince Edward Islands. NB1-j represents an uncultured candidate bacterial lineage that currently lacks a formally assigned phylum name. The SAR324 clade (Marine Group B) represents a marine bacterial lineage that has recently been proposed as a candidate phylum but remains taxonomically unresolved.

33. NEAR-SURFACE DISTRIBUTIONS OF PICOPHYTOPLANKTON IN THE SOUTHERN OCEAN

Picophytoplankton, the smallest phytoplankton size class, have a disproportionately large influence on phytoplankton community composition due to their rapid light absorption and reflection in surface waters. This report describes the near-surface distributions of three major groups of picophytoplankton, namely *Prochlorococcus* (typically abundant in warm, offshore waters), *Synechococcus* (usually dominant in coastal, nutrient-rich waters), and picoeukaryotes (generally common in upwelling areas) during an austral summer cruise in the Southern Ocean. These groups are known to respond differently to environmental changes due to their size and pigments.

Figure 1. Map showing sampled positions of surface abundance measurements of *Synechococcus* between South Africa (SA) and Antarctica. The black dots are sampling positions, and the black triangle indicates the location of the Prince Edward Islands.

Sampling was conducted between South Africa (SA) and 60°S from the underway seawater supply, and surface samples were collected from CTD casts along the Antarctic shelf during the 2024/2025 South African National Antarctic Expedition (SANAE; Fig. 1). Underway sampling was conducted eight times a day, using South African Standard Time (UTC+2) at 6 am, then at 12 pm and thereafter every two hours until midnight (12 am) for five days. Samples were prefiltered through a 200 μ m mesh, subdivided into triplicate aliquots, and thereafter preserved and stored frozen for analysis. Analyses were conducted using a flow cytometer, with lasers operating at different wavelengths, to count cells according to their size and pigment.

Prochlorococcus was the most abundant picophytoplankton group, reaching a maximum of 22,884 cells mL^{-1} , followed by *Synechococcus*, with a maximum of 19,571 cells mL^{-1} (Fig. 2). Picoeukaryotes were least abundant, with a maximum concentration of 1,005 cells mL^{-1} . Higher cell abundances were observed at night between SA and the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs), whereas lower abundances were observed during daylight hours between the PEIs and 60°S, particularly for *Synechococcus* (Figs. 1 and 2). Days 1 and 2 showed the highest cell counts for all picophytoplankton groups from 40°S to ca. 42°S, within the Agulhas Current region (Fig. 2a). On day 4, between 51°S and 53.8°S in the Southern Ocean, there was a gradual increase in cell counts throughout the day from early morning to midnight (Fig. 2a).

The distribution of picophytoplankton revealed clear differences in abundance among groups. The observed diel cycles, with higher abundances at night, suggest strong light-driven rhythms in picophytoplankton activity. Regional differences, such as high abundances in the Agulhas Current and gradual increases in the Southern Ocean, may be due to the influence of different oceanographic conditions on picophytoplankton distribution. Together, these findings suggest a relationship between biological rhythms of picophytoplankton and physical oceanographic conditions. However, further research is required to confirm this.

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Figure 2. Picophytoplankton group abundances (cells mL^{-1}) during (a) underway sampling, and (b) CTD sampling during the SANAE 2024/2025 expedition.

34. DISTRIBUTION OF PICOPHYTOPLANKTON NEAR ANTARCTICA IN JANUARY 2025

The Southern Ocean is dominated by the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC), the strongest and longest ocean current in the world. The ACC transports and mixes distinct water masses within and between Southern Ocean sectors, promoting the supply of nutrients to surface waters and supporting recurring plankton blooms. Although picophytoplankton have been investigated in the Southern Ocean, relatively few studies have focused on group-specific distributions. Here, we present a pilot study aimed at advancing microbial ecology research in Antarctic waters. Specifically, the study examines the spatial distribution of the three major picophytoplankton groups, *Synechococcus* and *Prochlorococcus* (both prokaryotes), and picoeukaryotes.

Figure 1. Map showing surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at stations (black dots) near Antarctica where samples were collected in January 2025.

Seawater samples were collected from the surface (ca. 5–7 m depth) and from the depths of maximum fluorescence (fmax), which varied from 12.2 to 84.6 m depth, at 15 stations near Antarctica (Fig. 1). Nine stations were located west of the Greenwich Meridian (GM; 0° longitude), with six stations to the east. Samples were preserved and frozen until further analysis. Sample analysis was conducted with a flow cytometer to acquire cell count data, which was used to calculate abundance (cells mL^{-1}).

The water was generally colder (between -0.75 and -0.25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) at all the stations east of the GM. In contrast, there were a few stations with surface water $>0^{\circ}\text{C}$ between 67 and 68°S to the west of the GM (Fig. 1). The vertical distributions of cell abundance from these stations are shown in Figure 2. Higher abundances of picoeukaryotes were observed at the fmax, while lower abundances were found at the surface, but there was less difference between depths for the other two groups (Fig. 2). Abundance of picoeukaryotes (maximum of $3,424$ cells mL^{-1}), the largest of the three groups in terms of cell size, was less than one third of that of *Prochlorococcus* with a maximum abundance of $12,757$ cells mL^{-1} (Fig 2).

Picoeukaryote abundances were higher at Station AMO1594 (west of the GM), and at Stations AMO1595 and AMO1596 (east of the GM), but were much lower at the other stations. The two prokaryote groups displayed higher abundances at stations located along

Figure 2. Picophytoplankton abundances at the surface and at the fmax for the three major groups, (a) picoeukaryotes, (b) *Synechococcus*, and (c) *Prochlorococcus*.

67.5°S (Figs. 2b,c), showing coexistence, while picoeukaryotes (Fig. 2a) were less abundant at these stations. This pattern reflects their contrasting environmental preferences, with prokaryotes favouring the warmer, high-light surface waters along 67.5°S , while picoeukaryotes were more abundant in deeper (fmax), colder, lower-light environments at stations south of 67.5°S . Together, these distributions underscore the ecological partitioning of the picophytoplankton communities. Our findings highlight how differing light and temperature conditions shape the spatial distribution of picophytoplankton and emphasise the need to consider both vertical and horizontal environmental variability when assessing oceanic picophytoplankton distributions.

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35. INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON PELAGIC ECOREGIONALISATION OF THE INDIAN SUB-ANTARCTIC HIGH SEAS

Ecoregionalisation is the process of partitioning an ecosystem into smaller ecoregions based on shared ecological, biophysical and biogeographical characteristics, to support conservation and other area-use strategies. A pelagic ecoregionalisation initiative for the sub-Antarctic Indian Ocean region was launched at a workshop in South Africa in 2019. This initiative evolved into the PHOCIS (Pelagic High seas Ocean eCoregionalisation of the Indian Subantarctic) project, an international scientific collaboration that includes governmental agencies, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and universities.

PHOCIS comprises six work packages: (1) Pelagic ecoregionalisation, (2) Connectivity between ecoregions, (3) Historical and forecasting trends, (4) Integrated Ocean Management, (5) Research and monitoring, and (6) Education and knowledge dissemination. Workshops are held annually, focusing on the distribution of plankton, mesopelagic fish, seabirds and marine mammals to inform conservation planning. A central feature of PHOCIS is the active involvement of postgraduate students and Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs), who work alongside senior scientists to achieve program goals.

The most recent workshop was held in Cape Town from 25–29 August 2025 (<https://www.sanap.ac.za/phocis-2025>). It was attended by 69 participants from various countries (54 in person, with others online), including Australia, Belgium, Brazil, France, Germany, India, South Africa, UK and USA (Fig. 1). A key objective of the 2025 workshop was to advance the discussion on integrated ocean management, including policy and legal considerations associated with developing a representative system of Marine Protected Area (MPA) declarations. This was addressed through a Systematic Conservation Planning approach (SCP).

The participants considered a range of conservation objectives pertinent to biogeographic areas and species assemblages in the study area (Fig. 2), such as identifying areas with significant prey for seabirds and marine mammals. As several of these predators are threatened by climate change and human activities, understanding their habitats is critical for effective conservation efforts. The SCP approach relies on data layers from key components of the pelagic ecoregions to identify priority areas and habitats for protection.

Figure 1. Participants at the PHOCIS Workshop held in Cape Town from 25–29 August 2025.

Parallel sessions were held to facilitate presentation of potential plankton, fish and predator data layers. The draft conservation objectives agreed on will enable the identification of priority species, assemblages, ecosystems, and ecoregions for the development of spatial layers to inform the SCP process. They will also support the selection of appropriate indicators for regional monitoring and help guide future research toward priority issues in the Indian sub-Antarctic. The objectives are expected to evolve through continued stakeholder engagement and scientific peer review.

Participants also identified potential human impacts in the region, developed a strategic approach to spatial planning with a view to proposing MPAs, and reviewed the legal and governance frameworks necessary for effective implementation. The SCP is expected to make a significant contribution to CCAMLR's (Council for the Conservation of Antarctic Living Marine Resources) goal of establishing a representative system of MPAs within its jurisdiction.

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Figure 2. The PHOCIS study area (20°W–160°E; 30–60°S), and the Systematic Conservation Planning domain (20–150°E; 40–60°S).

36. SOUTH AFRICA AT THE FOREFRONT: NUCLEAR SCIENCE SOLUTIONS FOR PLASTIC POLLUTION

Plastic pollution poses a growing threat to marine ecosystems, biodiversity, human health, tourism and fisheries, with developing regions disproportionately affected by limited monitoring capacity and uneven access to advanced technologies. In South Africa and across Africa, persistent data gaps, lack of harmonised monitoring protocols, and limited infrastructure constrain effective reporting, policy implementation, and participation in global processes such as Sustainable Development Goal 14.1.1b and ongoing negotiations towards a legally binding global plastics treaty (Fig. 1). Nuclear Technology for Controlling Plastic Pollution (NUTEC Plastics) is a flagship initiative for member states of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) that applies nuclear science to monitor and address plastic pollution in the marine environment.

Figure 1. Science issues in Africa related to plastics information and policy generation.

DFFE participated in the International High-Level Forum on NUTEK Plastics, hosted by the IAEA and the Government of the Philippines (25–26 November 2025). South Africa was invited to present both national perspectives and regional progress, including a Ministerial statement reflecting its engagement as the G20 Chair (2024–2025) (Fig. 2), and technical contributions on marine plastics monitoring (Fig. 3). The programme included Ministerial dialogues, technical sessions on nuclear-enabled marine monitoring and radiation-based plastic upcycling, and discussions on regional capacity-building. Key scientific and policy outcomes are summarised below:

- **Global method harmonisation:** Strong alignment emerged among the IAEA, UNEP, the EU Joint Research Centre and Japan on standardised protocols for monitoring beach litter, microplastics and marine debris, directly supporting SDG 14.1.1b reporting.
- **Nuclear-enabled monitoring:** Advanced nuclear techniques (e.g. isotope tracing) were demonstrated as reliable tools for quantifying microplastics and identifying pollution sources in marine environments.
- **Circular economy innovation:** Radiation-based plastic upcycling (e.g. electron beam irradiation) was showcased as a viable approach for converting low-value plastic waste into high-strength construction and industrial materials.
- **African leadership:** South Africa highlighted the unique challenges facing African countries and advocated for capacity-building models tailored to limited laboratory resources, long supply chains

Figure 2. DFFE's Deputy Minister Swarts addressing the Forum with a national statement and as the current G20 chair.

and socioeconomic constraints, thereby promoting equity and inclusivity in global science initiatives.

- **Capacity building:** More than 100 Member States now participate in NUTEK Plastics, with over 400 scientists trained and over 70 laboratories equipped, presenting strategic opportunities for South Africa and the broader African region.

The outcomes of the Forum align directly with DFFE priorities in marine environmental monitoring, evidence-based policy, and circular economy transition. Harmonised monitoring protocols strengthen South Africa's national data systems and international reporting obligations, while nuclear-enabled methodologies offer innovative solutions to persistent monitoring gaps. Radiation-based upcycling technologies support national waste-to-value strategies, Extended Producer Responsibility implementation, and green industry development. South Africa is strategically positioned to champion science-policy integration, technology transfer, and equitable capacity development across Africa and the Global South.

Figure 3. Keshnee Pillay (DFFE) addressing the Forum on South Africa's and Africa's research.

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37. HARMONISING UNITED NATIONS PROTOCOLS FOR MONITORING PLASTIC POLLUTION

South Africa unifies two authoritative frameworks into one coherent standard for field sampling, laboratory workflows, and reporting of plastic pollution (Fig. 1). These are (i) the Joint Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection’s (GESAMP, a United Nations (UN) scientific advisory body) “Guidelines for the Monitoring and Assessment of Plastic Litter in the Ocean”, and (ii) the UN International Atomic Energy Agency’s (IAEA) NUTEC Plastics (Nuclear TEChnology for Controlling Plastic Pollution) marine microplastics protocols. The harmonised method covers sampling design, indicator selection, sample collection and handling, material characterisation, uncertainty management, and standardised reporting formats.

Figure 1. OC Research team testing a field sampling design that merges GESAMP and IAEA field protocols.

National surveys on beaches will now follow a unified protocol (Fig. 2). Standard kits and common laboratory procedures ensure reproducible, high-quality datasets suitable for trend detection and management decisions. Harmonised datasets reduce uncertainty and improve confidence in national reporting on coastal plastic debris trends, supporting evidence-based policy and budgeting. South Africa serves as a national centre of excellence and a regional hub for the IAEA for microplastics monitoring, embedding skills, and sound laboratory systems.

Comparable Microplastics Monitoring of Oceans (COMMON) is a UN Ocean Decade-endorsed project led by South Africa (DFFE: OC Research) that translates this harmonised methodology into a coordinated continental project (Fig. 3). Participating countries adopt standard protocols to generate comparable datasets across Africa. Comparable measurements in beach sand establish a continental baseline for plastic pollution abundance and composition, enabling assessment of change over time.

Figure 2. Beach sampling grid that merges GESAMP and IAEA NUTEC Plastics guidelines, and that will be implemented under the DFFE’s Macro-, Meso-, Micro-Plastics (SAMP) Network.

The NUTEC Plastics initiative provides countries with training, standard kits, and Quality Assurance/Quality Control support, to facilitate an African microplastics monitoring network.

Figure 3. Shown in green are the 19 African countries aiming to adopt a COMMON method by 2030. The 2 countries shown in yellow are working towards joining the network.

The COMMON project advances Ocean Decade Challenge 1 (Understand and Beat Marine Pollution) and contributes to challenges on ecosystem restoration and expanding global ocean observing. Evidence generated will inform national and regional policies on marine litter reduction, extended producer responsibility, and coastal management. Harmonised data streams will feed SDG 14.1.1b portals and inform international marine litter negotiations and monitoring frameworks. Data products will align with open, accessible and decision-ready information, and standardised metadata will support cross-portal discoverability and FAIR principles (improve the findability accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data).

By integrating the guidelines and protocols of GESAMP with IAEA workflows, and deploying them via COMMON project, South Africa is enabling a single, coherent global dataset for beach plastic pollution. South Africa invites partners across government, industry and academia to align projects with the harmonised protocol, to co-invest in sustained monitoring, and to use COMMON’s continental network to accelerate plastic pollution monitoring.

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38. DNA MINI-BARCODE PRIMERS IMPROVE SPECIES DETECTION RATES IN METABARCODING OF MARINE ZOOPLANKTON

DNA metabarcoding combines next-generation sequencing technologies with online barcode reference libraries to simultaneously identify multiple species in taxonomically diverse samples. This approach is recognised as a powerful tool for assessing biodiversity in marine pelagic ecosystems. However, its application in South Africa remains relatively limited.

Figure 1. Comparison of Phred quality scores obtained for four zooplankton taxa using three different primers: standard (COI), universal COI mini-barcode (MICOintF), and taxon-specific mini-barcode (MB). Black dots indicate individual samples with unusually high- or low-quality scores.

Bulk marine zooplankton samples collected using towed nets contain degraded or fragmented DNA due to environmental exposure and sampling processes. Zooplankton metabarcoding allows for the detection of cryptic species, damaged specimens, and multiple life stages that lack clear morphological diagnostic features, such as eggs and larvae. The use of mini-barcode primers (<350 base pairs) increases the likelihood of successful DNA amplification and species detection when compared to standard full-length primers (ca. 650 base pairs). Despite their shorter lengths, mini-barcodes retain sufficient sequence variability to enable species-level resolution and are well suited to high-throughput sequencing platforms.

Species detection in metabarcoding datasets may be underestimated due to primer bias or incomplete barcode reference libraries. To overcome these limitations and improve the detection of key zooplankton groups such as copepods, euphausiids, chaetognaths and hydrozoans, novel taxon-specific mini-barcode primers were designed targeting the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene region, the most widely used genetic marker for DNA barcoding of marine zooplankton. Publicly available COI sequences were downloaded from the Barcode of Life Data System and GenBank and analysed *in silico* to identify highly variable and taxonomically informative regions for each target

group. Selected gene regions (250–350 base pairs) were evaluated using DNA barcode gap analyses to confirm their suitability for species-level discrimination. Mini-barcode primers were then designed for each target group. The performance of the newly designed primers was tested against standard COI primers and a universal COI mini-barcode primer using DNA extracted from target voucher specimens. Across all target taxa, the taxon-specific mini-barcode primers outperformed both comparison primers, yielding higher-quality sequences and improved amplification success, as reflected by higher Phred quality scores (Fig. 1).

Figure 2. Bar graph showing species richness across zooplankton taxonomic groups. Blue bars indicate taxa for which specific primers were used and red bars indicate non-targeted taxa.

Four bulk zooplankton samples collected during a 2022 research cruise aboard the *SA Agulhas II* in the Agulhas Bank region were analysed using metabarcoding. Using a combination of the newly designed taxon-specific primers with the universal primer, we identified 220 zooplankton species across 15 different taxonomic groups (Fig. 2). This combined approach improved species detection in towed net samples, increasing the proportional representation of target taxa by three- to fivefold compared with studies that used only universal primers. Overall, this study demonstrates that integrating universal and taxon-specific mini-barcode primers within metabarcoding workflows provides a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of zooplankton biodiversity. The primer design framework developed here can be readily applied to additional taxonomic groups and marine environments, enhancing species-level resolution and strengthening the capacity for ecological research and long-term biodiversity monitoring.

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39. A CROWDSOURCED GILLNET REPORTING APPLICATION TO SUPPORT COASTAL COMPLIANCE AND ENFORCEMENT

Gillnetting is a form of passive fishing where nets most often extend the entire vertical water column, held in place by weights at the bottom and floats on the surface. This ‘net wall’ indiscriminately traps various animals including fish, mammals and birds, resulting in excessive bycatch (Fig. 1). Gillnets are also often lost when swept away or intentionally discarded, polluting the environment and acting as ghost nets that continue to trap and kill marine and freshwater life. Consequently, in the early 2000s, the South African government committed to outlawing the use of gillnetting in estuaries and freshwater bodies due to the negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity. Today, limited permissible use of gillnets is regulated through permits.

Figure 1. A juvenile cormorant entangled in a gillnet. Image credit: Durban Metro Police.

While gillnetting remains a problem, specifically in KwaZulu-Natal, the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) in collaboration with WILDTRUST, developed a publicly accessible reporting application that allows gillnetting observations to be reported directly to the relevant authorities. Consultation surrounding the development of the tool took place in 2025 and highlighted the needs of various stakeholders who contribute to law enforcement efforts, including the requirements from scientists involved in fish stock monitoring.

The overarching sentiment expressed during these consultations was: 1) the need for a single reporting mechanism where the public, as ‘eyes-on-the-ground’, can contribute to the eradication of gillnetting in a manner that is both efficient and safe; 2) that various law enforcement stakeholders have a consolidated view of the data being submitted to assist in planning formal operations; and 3) that the impact of gillnetting on marine resources can better inform fish stock management.

The technological considerations in achieving such a tool include having a system through which any member of the public can submit data, while systems dedicated to compliance initiatives remain safeguarded from unauthorised access. As such, a public-facing application was developed by the DFFE’s Oceans and Coastal Information Management System (OCIMS) team and hosted on DFFE infrastructure. The receiving system, the National Environmental Crime Database (CMORE), is hosted externally. Communication between the two systems is achieved through an application programming interface.

The public-facing gillnet reporting form can be accessed via a QR code or directly through the OCIMS website:

(https://ocims.environment.gov.za/Gillnet_response.html) and allows users to report the location of incidents, catch quantity, fishing gear observed, amongst others. The form utilises dropdown menus and tick-box options to standardise data and limit the need for user-based text responses (Fig. 2). This data standardisation technique allows data to be used and analysed immediately, which facilitates the rapid identification of insights through the open dashboard. Dashboards have proven useful in communicating high-level data trends (e.g. identifying hotspots and species caught), and to create public awareness.

 A screenshot of a mobile application interface titled 'Gillnet Reporting'. The form is divided into two main sections: 'Observations' and 'Descriptions of fish observed'.

 Under 'Observations', there is a question 'How many people did you observe gillnetting, if any?' with a text input field containing the number '4'. Below this are two questions with radio button options: 'Are you able to describe the paraphernalia observed (i.e. craft, nets, buckets, paddles)?' with 'Yes' selected, and 'Are you able to provide information regarding any fish caught?' with 'Yes' selected.

 Under 'Descriptions of fish observed', there is a field for 'Group / common name' with a search box containing 'Bream'. Below this is a 'Species' section with three radio button options: 'River bream/perch', 'Natal stumpnose/ yellowfin bream', and 'Estuarine bream', with 'Estuarine bream' selected. At the bottom, there is a field for 'Total fish of this species' with a text input containing '6'.

Figure 2. An example of data captured on the gillnetting form through the interface on a smartphone.

While not the first reporting tool of its kind, the gillnet reporting form and its integration with CMORE represents a breakthrough in addressing environmental crimes in South Africa by enabling public contributions to flow directly into a database traditionally reserved for law enforcement officials. It is envisaged that having more ‘eyes-on-the-ground’ will improve compliance and enforcement efforts pertaining to illegal gillnetting. While a ‘soft-launch’ has taken place, further public awareness campaigns are envisaged.

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40. BUILDING CAPACITY FOR CONTINUOUS PLANKTON RECORDER SAMPLE ANALYSIS

The Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) is a robust, torpedo-shaped plankton sampling instrument designed to be towed from merchant vessels on their normal shipping routes, enabling basin-scale mapping of near-surface plankton. Plankton are trapped between two layers of silk, which are spooled together and preserved in formalin for subsequent laboratory analysis. The CPR Survey has been operating in the North Atlantic since 1931, making it one of the longest-running marine biological monitoring programmes in the world, providing valuable insights into long-term and climate-related changes in the marine food web.

South Africa initiated regular CPR tows in the Southern Ocean in 2011, during annual relief voyages to the Prince Edward Islands in autumn, Antarctica in summer, and Gough Island in spring. Since then, CPR tows by DFFE (the SA-CPR Survey) have spanned over 55,000 nautical miles, with over 100 silks collected. However, none have been analysed due to the lack of suitable laboratory facilities to process the formalin-preserved lengths of silk safely. The recent acquisition of a containerised laboratory with fume extraction capacity has now enabled analysis to proceed.

A 3-day “Continuous Plankton Recorder and Imaging Workshop” was held in Cape Town during September 2025 to equip DFFE staff with the skills required to initiate analysis of the SA-CPR silk repository (Fig. 1). Experts from France, Brazil and Australia presented methods used to process and analyse silks from CPR surveys in their respective countries. Practical sessions included cutting a silk from the Marion Island Relief 2018 survey into pre-determined segments, on-silk analysis of phytoplankton using an inverted microscope, and zooplankton identification under a stereo microscope. The imaging component of the

workshop included presentations on benchtop imaging processes using the ZooScan and FlowCam® Macro instruments. Both instruments were used in practical sessions to test their efficacy as a novel approach for rapid, semi-automated analysis of plankton washed from the CPR silks. This is known as off-silk analysis, which is traditionally conducted using a microscope. DFFE staff also demonstrated microplankton analysis using the FlowCam® VS-IV. Desktop practical sessions were held for satellite analysis of chlorophyll along the CPR tow routes, as an alternative to the Phytoplankton Colour Index (PCI) estimate of near-surface phytoplankton biomass, as well as for ZooScan data analysis. After the formal workshop, Claus Inck (Brazil) spent an extra day with the DFFE plankton team to demonstrate the calculations used to apportion the silks into segments representing regular tows-distance intervals, as well as to review overall CPR protocols. The workshop has laid a solid foundation for in-house CPR silk analysis to proceed.

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Figure 1. Clockwise, from top left: workshop participants; working with silk segments in the fume hood; demonstrating the FlowCam Macro; a segment of silk showing euphausiids (*Euphausia vallentini*) sampled near Marion Island; demonstrating on-silk analysis of phytoplankton.

41. STRENGTHENING SOUTH AFRICA'S PLASTICS MONITORING NETWORK: INSIGHTS FROM THE SAMP NETWORK WORKSHOP 2025

The DFFE's South African Macro-, Meso-, Micro-Plastics (SAMP) Network hosted a one-day national workshop during the 2025 Southern African Marine Science Symposium (SAMSS) (Fig. 1). The workshop brought together a diverse group of participants, including school learners, early-career researchers, and senior scientists from both within and beyond the plastics research community, reflecting the growing need for broad engagement in addressing plastic pollution (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. The team facilitating the SAMP workshop at SAMSS 2025: from left to right - M Worship, MS Soeker, S Setati, Y Hansraj, K Pillay (DFFE); T Mtontsi (SAEON, a National Research Foundation Facility); H Fieland (Polyco, a non-profit organisation making waste a value resource) and S du Preez (post-graduate student, DFFE-UCT).

Figure 2. Marco Worship (DFFE) presenting to SAMP workshop participants

Key workshop outcomes addressed four themes:

1. Strengthening Decision-Relevant Knowledge for Plastics Monitoring

Participants affirmed a strong need for standardised, cost-sensitive monitoring protocols and sentinel species selection frameworks, highlighting several key points:

- The need for a national sentinel suite covering trophic transfer of plastics from the coastal to open ocean.
- The need for accessible training on core laboratory methods such as visual sorting, density separation, and microscopy, including a phased approach to expand polymer identification capabilities across institutions.
- The role of workshops in providing hands-on exposure to monitoring tools, Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) requirements, and Quality Assurance/Quality Control considerations.

2. Bridging Impact Research with Community Understanding

Discussions underscored the value of platforms in translating complex impact pathways into publicly accessible knowledge. Priority areas included:

- Human health exposure pathways (air, water, seafood) and ecosystem-level impacts such as trophic transfer and biogeochemical disruption.
- Integrating community perspectives and improving scientific literacy to counter misinformation.
- The need for transdisciplinary dialogue between ecologists, social scientists, and public health researchers.

3. Empowering Storytelling, Education and Behaviour Change

Group outputs strongly emphasised culturally relevant communication, calling for:

- Visual and narrative tools informed by local scientific data (e.g. plastic ingestion rates in locally consumed seafood, such as mussels).
- Co-created educational resources such as comics, animations, songs, and community theatre that are validated by scientists to ensure accuracy.
- Science-backed behaviour-change mechanisms, e.g. designing learner programmes.

4. Inclusive, Multi-Stakeholder Capacity Development

Training and outreach were repeatedly identified as essential for enabling long-term plastics research. Participants recommended:

- National partnerships to support sampling and laboratory infrastructure needs.
- Community empowerment programmes enabling citizen science roles in monitoring.
- Collaborative spaces for industry, researchers, non-profit government organisations (NGOs), and school learners to shape monitoring priorities and mitigation strategies.

The workshop demonstrated that training and outreach are not peripheral. Instead, they are central enablers for scalable, comparable plastics monitoring and for advancing evidence-based impact research across South Africa. The highly engaged, intergenerational audience provided insights that will guide future national capacity-building initiatives under the SAMP Network.

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